

TANGENT

REPORT ON TANGENT FORUM ACTIVITIES

D1.5

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 955273

Deliverable administrative information

Deliverable number	1.5
Deliverable title	Report on TANGENT Forum activities
Dissemination level	Public
Submission deadline	31/10/2024
Version number	1.0
Authors	Dr. Lakshya Pandit, Daniel Franco (Rupprecht Consult)
Internal reviewers	Juliette Thijs (POLIS) Mark Meyer (POLIS) Lucie Tristant (ID4MOBILITY)
Document approval	N/A

Legal Disclaimer

TANGENT is co-funded by the European Commission, Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 955273 (Innovation Action). The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any specific purpose. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein. The TANGENT Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Copyright © TANGENT Consortium, 2024.

https://twitter.com/TANGENT_H2020

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/tangent-project/>

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhz4kwEm_sTHj7fE4zXToA

For further information please visit <http://www.tangent-h2020.eu/>

Executive summary

This deliverable focuses on the TANGENT Forum activities carried under Work Package 1 (WP1) i.e., multi-actor cooperation models & policies. Within Task 1.3 Stakeholder engagement and consultation, several TANGENT forum activities were executed, providing a platform ensuring feedback and consideration of perspectives from key stakeholders, steering knowledge exchange and synergies with other projects.

These activities include gathering public opinion through Mentimeter questions, presenting key project results and tools developed through virtual Webinar series, lessons learned and conclusions from the TANGENT Forum engagement. These engagements also include activities with Advisory Board members, whose feedback during the project's timeline assisted in defining key project aspects.

The deliverable presents itself as a medium to share the activities conducted within Task 1.3 through the TANGENT Forum and associated outcomes with links to the online repository for knowledge exchange and contributes in the understanding towards the developing field of traffic management.

Key words

Network traffic management, planning, regulatory framework, sustainable urban mobility planning, webinars, knowledge exchange

Table of contents

DELIVERABLE ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION.....	1
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS.....	6
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
2 WEBINARS	10
3 ADVISORY BOARD SESSIONS	33
4 POLICY RECOMMENDATION WORKSHOP.....	51
5 TANGENT FORUM ACTIVITIES ON MOBILITY ACADEMY	57
6 CONCLUSIONS.....	60
7 REFERENCES.....	61

List of figures

Figure 1: Dissemination through visuals on social media platforms e.g., LinkedIn (as provided by POLIS).....	11
Figure 2: Extract from the first poll using the Mentimeter platform.....	15
Figure 3: Extract from the second poll using the Mentimeter platform.....	15
Figure 4: Extract from the first poll using the Mentimeter platform.....	21
Figure 5: Extract from the second poll using the Mentimeter platform.....	21
Figure 6: Athens case study testing connection between Thrakomakedones region and the First District of Athens (Source: OpenStreetMap).....	24
Figure 7: Baseline scenario through TANGENT tool with key performance indicators in Manchester..	25
Figure 8: Optimised scenario through TANGENT tool with key performance indicators in Manchester.....	25
Figure 9: One of the iterations during arbitration between two prominent opinions (sp = service performance, ne = network efficiency, ep = economic performance, env = environmental performance).....	26
Figure 10: Objective weights for different strategies.....	27
Figure 11: Extract from the first poll using the Mentimeter platform.....	27
Figure 12: TANGENT Dashboard as presented by Tiago Dias during the Webinar.....	30
Figure 13: Mentimeter responses from the first poll.....	32
Figure 14: Extract from WP3 presentation of the meeting, highlighting the topics for the discussion..	37
Figure 15: Extract from project presentation for the meeting.....	41
Figure 16: Flowchart of TANGENT Services and corresponding Functionalities.....	42
Figure 17: Flowchart depicting Real-time traffic management framework.....	43
Figure 18: Data set showing speed in 5-minute time stamp for Greater Manchester through loop detectors.....	43
Figure 19: Miro Board frame used for the first discussion session.....	45
Figure 20: Flowchart of tools including COD and consensus reaching mechanisms.....	47
Figure 21: TANGENT Forum Sections on Mobility Academy.....	58
Figure 22: Discussion Forum on Smart Infrastructure Classification Index.....	59
Figure 23: Snapshots from project deliverables as provided by POLIS.....	59

List of tables

Table 1: Webinar schedule for the four-part series.....	10
Table 2: Webinar 1 Agenda.....	11
Table 3: Webinar 2 Agenda.....	17
Table 4: Webinar 3 Agenda.....	23
Table 5: Webinar 4 Agenda.....	29
Table 6: AB Sessions and Format in TANGENT.....	35

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AB	Advisory Board
CAVs	Connected and Automated Vehicles
COD	Computer Optimised Design
DCP	Dynamic Congestion Pricing
DRT	Demand Responsive Transport
DRT-PT Sync	Synchronisation of DRT and Transit modes
DRT-TC Sync	Synchronisation of DRT and Traffic Control
EC	European Commission
EC	European Commission
FCD	Floating Car Data
GA	Grant Agreement
ISAD	Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MTGNN	Multivariate Time Series Forecasting with Graph Neural Networks

Acronym	Meaning
NAPs	National Access Points
NPSE	Transport Project provider companies
NTM	Network and Traffic Management
O/D Matrices	Origin-Destination Matrices
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PT	Public Transport
PT-TC Sync	Synchronisation of Public Transport and Traffic Control
RTTI	Real-Time Traffic Information
SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan
SVCC	Signal-Vehicle Couple Control
TEN-T	Trans European Transport Network
TfGM	Transport for Greater Manchester
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Overview of the project and the deliverable

The TANGENT project, part of the EU Horizon 2020 research initiative, focuses on developing innovative tools for Network and Traffic Management (NTM) that incorporate multi-actor cooperation models to address the complexities of urban mobility. This deliverable (D1.5) documents the outcomes of various stakeholder engagement and consultation activities conducted throughout the project, including virtual forums, webinars, and workshops. These interactions provided insights from diverse actors such as policymakers, city authorities, transport operators, and researchers to support the development and implementation of NTM solutions in Europe. The deliverable also serves as a knowledge-sharing platform to encourage collaborative approaches to traffic management and provide guidance for future projects. The deliverable is part of Task 1.3 'Stakeholder engagement and consultation', which aims to coordinate the engagement and consultation of external stakeholders and experts.

1.2 Intended audience

This is a public deliverable where activities performed aimed to maximise outreach of the project's results. The primary audience for this deliverable includes policymakers, local authorities, and practitioners involved in urban mobility planning and traffic management. Additionally, it is intended for researchers, industry stakeholders, and project partners who are engaged in developing cooperative traffic management systems.

1.3 Objectives of the deliverable

The objectives of this deliverable are to summarise the activities and outcomes of the TANGENT Forum, present lessons learned from activities including webinars (involving feedback questions, Q&As, and polls), workshops, advisory board sessions, and provide links to materials developed (e.g., webinar recordings, workshop results, and dissemination material developed).

The report aims to document how TANGENT reached out to different organisations and projects, researchers, authorities and industries, city representatives and users in general, to set up a TANGENT Forum and establish a structured cooperation strategy based on mutual benefit. Aiming to maximise outreach, different sets of activities were executed under Task 1.3, which has been documented in this deliverable.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured into six main chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction – Provides an overview of the project and deliverable.

Chapter 2: Webinars – Presents the outcomes of a four-part webinar series on NTM, with discussions ranging from real-time traffic modelling to decision-making tools.

Chapter 3: Advisory Board Sessions – Focuses on the role of the advisory board in guiding TANGENT's progress, offering strategic advice and market insights.

Chapter 4: Policy Recommendation Workshop – Discusses the key findings from the policy recommendation workshop, highlighting three key aspects i.e., exploitation of MTM solutions / TANGENT tools, policies and regulations: gaps and recommendations, and further research needs and open questions.

Chapter 5: TANGENT Forum Activities on Mobility Academy – Details the activities and knowledge exchange within the TANGENT Forum, hosted on the Mobility Academy platform, including discussions and collaborative efforts.

Chapter 6: Conclusions – Summarises the main takeaways from the deliverable.

2 Webinars

The Webinar Chapter introduces a series of interactive online sessions hosted by the TANGENT project, aimed at disseminating key findings, tools, and outcomes developed throughout the project. These webinars foster knowledge exchange and active engagement with stakeholders, including policymakers, transport operators, and industry experts, offering an open platform for discussion and collaboration on cooperative traffic management solutions.

Each webinar covers a specific aspect of Network Traffic Management (NTM), from real-time modelling and forecasting to optimising transport networks and arbitration models, and integrated tool for cooperative traffic management. Through live presentations (via MS Teams), Q&A sessions, and interactive tools such as Mentimeter polls, participants were encouraged to provide feedback and insights. These webinars served as both an informative and participatory space to deepen understanding of the innovative approaches TANGENT proposes to tackle urban mobility challenges and improve traffic systems across European cities.

2.1 Schedule, topics and participation

The four-part Webinar series was kickstarted during the month of November in 2023, with the topic focusing on Network and Traffic Management. The schedule for the four-part Webinar series, including the topics and number of participants, is shared as follows:

Date	Webinar	Participants
15.11.2023	Webinar 1: Navigating through Network and Traffic Management: An Urban Phenomenon	42
31.01.2024	Webinar 2: Real-Time Traffic Modelling and Forecasting Tools	65
21.05.2024	Webinar 3: Transport Network Optimisation and Arbitration Models	36
30.10.2024	Webinar 4: Integrated Tool for Cooperative Traffic Management and Results of Case Study Implementation	16

Table 1: Webinar schedule for the four-part series

Webinar 1 aimed to understand the approach towards Network and Traffic Management, which influences policy and decision-making processes leading to on-site and off-site implications. It addressed the approach by focusing on cities including one of the TANGENT Case Studies in Greater Manchester, where the project solutions are being tested.

Webinar 2 addressed the technical aspects of network and traffic management by looking into the corresponding tools and framework. This involved forecasting tools and data quality along with the framework for real-time traffic management. It includes both supply prediction and demand estimation and prediction. This Webinar was the first of the two technical Webinars within the TANGENT project and presented key results with further engagement opportunities via TANGENT Forum (more information in Chapter 5).

Webinar 3 focused on the development of a framework for transport network-wide optimisation considering both current and future mobility solutions. In TANGENT, the framework developed will take into account the preferences and needs of multiple actors involved in transport network management. This includes development of arbitration models to balance their particular needs in different scenarios.

Figure 1: Dissemination through visuals on social media platforms e.g., LinkedIn (as provided by POLIS)

The final Webinar in the four-part series covered two crucial topics: the decision-making support tool for managing traffic operations and the outcomes from the four TANGENT case studies. The discussion on the tool put emphasis on its design and development, particularly with the creation of a unified dashboard for multimodal traffic management. The solutions have been implemented in four TANGENT case studies: Athens, Greater Manchester, Lisbon, and Rennes. The key results were showcased, marking the conclusion of the TANGENT Webinar series.

2.2 Webinar 1: Navigating through Network and Traffic Management: An Urban Phenomenon

2.2.1 Welcome and agenda

Lakshya Pandit from Rupprecht Consult welcomed the Webinar attendees kickstarting the first TANGENT Webinar in the four-part series. Prior information regarding the technical logistics during the Webinar was given to the attendees, followed by an introduction to the TANGENT project. The goals and agenda of the Webinar were later shared, followed by the introduction of the two speakers i.e., Laura Babío Somoza from POLIS and Hannah Tune from Transport for Greater Manchester.

Table 2: Webinar 1 Agenda

Time	Description	Speake
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome and Introduction Agenda, Aim, Speakers, TANGENT project, Technical guidance	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)
	Poll 1	

Time	Description	Speake
14:10 - 14:25	Presentation 1: Multimodal Network Management in Urban Areas	Laura Babío Somoza (POLIS)
14:25 - 14:30	Questions and Answers for Presentation 1	
14:30 - 14:45	Presentation 2: Network and Traffic Management: A TfGM Perspective	Hannah Tune (TfGM)
14:45 - 14:50	Questions and Answers for Presentation 2	
14:50 - 15:00	Poll 2	
	Concluding remarks and next activities TANGENT Webinar Series and Forum	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)

2.2.2 Presentation session

2.2.2.1 Towards Multimodal Network Management in Urban Areas

Laura Babío Somoza from POLIS, a TANGENT partner, presented her topic for the first presentation titled '*Towards Multimodal Network Management in Urban Areas*'. The introductory section focused on how POLIS works on sustainable transport innovations including Mobility and Traffic Efficiency. This was followed by tackling the subject of urban transport through its main challenges and goals, which is common among many cities. This includes air quality, where cities and urban areas have poorer air quality than non-urbanized areas. A disproportionate amount of space dedicated to cars causes congestion but also facilitates a high number of accidents and fatalities in the road with many victims being vulnerable road users (VRUs) (including pedestrians, cyclists, and two-wheelers). Consequently, the goals of the cities around Europe are also similar i.e., improving air quality, increasing road safety, and promoting a modal shift towards active and sustainable modes. These are also the priorities that the traffic management measures respond to. The objective is to manage traffic, i.e., to manage the flow of people and goods with strategies, plans, and technology.

It was shown how traditional traffic management is car-centric, neglecting alternative and sustainable transport, fragmented (as it does not consider different modes, leading to a lack of coordination between planning and operation), unsafe (for VRUs), and inefficient. The multimodal network management is holistic (integrating different modes), proactive, smart, environmentally responsive, safe, and equitable in its approach. Following this, a comprehensive traffic/network management overview was shared. This includes elements such as traffic circulation plans (e.g., UVAR i.e., Urban Vehicle Access Regulation), dynamic traffic management measures (e.g., strategies that depend on unplanned events like accidents), road classification framework, traffic signal plan, public transport integration, parking management strategies, active mobility structure integration, real-time monitoring, ITS (i.e., Intelligent Transportation System), and functional road classification schemes.

An example of multimodal network management was shared through the city of Groningen, aiming to be a liveable, clean, and healthy city. This is done not through building new infrastructure but by making better use of the infrastructure that they already have. Two documents were shared which included

Multimodal Network Framework Groningen (2023) and Traffic Light Policy Plan Groningen (2023). The first document included mapping of the main destinations in the city and the preferred routes to reach each destination in different modes, which also included functional profiles for different roads. While the first document is focused more on the network level, the second document focuses on the street level. The second document includes an installation strategy along with the maintenance strategy for traffic lights.

Following the Groningen example, the EU policy to drive ITS implementation was shared through the ITS Directive (2010) and RTTI Delegated Regulation. The former aims to increase the deployment and use of ITS services across the European Union, and it was recently reviewed to account for innovations such as Autonomous Vehicles (AV) or Mobility as a Service (MaaS). Following the ITS Directive, there were a series of delegated regulations to legislate on more specific issues within ITS. One of them is the Real-Time Traffic Information, which aims to increase the provision of data to enable multimodal network management in a coordinated way. This was also recently reviewed to include urban areas, as earlier it focused on highways and motorways.

Towards the end, Laura stressed the implications at the urban level, which included more obligations on road authorities to publish data when it is digitally available, the mandate to digitise certain 'crucial data types', obligations on service providers to provide (in-vehicle generated) data to public authorities as major points. Projects including TANGENT, have joined forces in a cluster that is called 4Front Cluster, collaborating and working in the traffic management and the data domain.

Following links were shared during the presentation:

- Multimodal Network Framework Groningen (2023):
<https://gemeenteraad.groningen.nl/Documenten/Bijlage-1-Multimodaal-Netwerkkader-Hoofdrapport.pdf>
- Traffic Light Policy Plan Groningen (2023):
<https://gemeenteraad.groningen.nl/Documenten/Documenten/Bijlage-3-Beleidsplan-Verkeerslichten.pdf>

2.2.2.2 Network and Traffic Management: A TfGM Perspective

Hannah Tune from Transport for Greater Manchester (TfGM), a TANGENT partner from one of the four case study cities, presented her topic in the presentation titled '*Network and Traffic Management: A TfGM Perspective*'. The introductory section focused on what TfGM does, which included managing all transport activity i.e., from managing tram network to active travel, coordinating road works and controlling traffic lights, and more. Following this, the Greater Manchester 2040 Transport Strategy was shared by Hannah. The vision is for 50% of all journeys in Greater Manchester to be made by walking, cycling, and public transport by 2040. This will involve desired outcomes including (but not limited to) predictable journey times, safe routes for cyclists and pedestrians, healthy travel options, and efficient, predictable public transport, accessible to all.

Example solutions that deliver outcomes through the use of ITS and integrated systems were shared which included using proven algorithms and data analytics to predict congestions, implementing actions using Variable Message Signage (VMS), and other customer information systems, using sensors to monitor VRU movements and driver behaviours, Pedestrian SCOOT, optimising signals which reduces waiting time for pedestrians, sharing data between multiple third-party systems across modes of transport (e.g., Bus Open Data) and more. Following the previous examples, the national approach in the UK Department for Transport to better use data and technology was focused upon. This included examples like the Manual for Smart Streets (MfSS) where the management, operation, and maintenance of streets and highways are enhanced through the application of technology; and Digital

Local Roads, where digitization strengthens mobility transition and makes mobility more efficient, smoother, and safer.

The case study focus of Greater Manchester in the TANGENT project was later shared, where it looks upon the optimisation of transport flows including connectivity between urban and rural regions, followed by priorities for the use cases i.e., increasing use of sustainable modes, reducing transport emissions, reducing congestion, improving connectivity between modes, and improving customer information. Some of the challenges include managing congestion, encouraging a modal shift to sustainable modes, understanding how future mobility can shape transport systems, and integrating traffic management systems. Part of the process of building the case study was by engaging with stakeholders through TANGENT.

Following this, a quick overview was shared on the kind of data and technology the TfGM Operational Control Centre manages daily. This included approximately 2500 traffic signals, various assets on the highway network, CCTV, VMS for sharing information to the customers, different sensing technology, roadworks/events/incidents, and more. The Bee network (a TfGM Network) acknowledges that the data and technology can help with customer information, connected mobility, intelligent network management capabilities, and more. The current network management assistance from the ITS platform was shared, which included existing assets (e.g., VMS, CCTV), Open data (e.g., Bus Open Data, roadworks, floating vehicle data), and future data sets (e.g., CAV data, AQ Sensors). This would provide tools for strategic multimodal interventions, enhance customer information, and improve the efficiency and coordination of highway networks. Lastly, building on the foundations of the current technologies, systems, and expertise, the roadmap to outline the future of ITS for Greater Manchester was shared. This included the current capabilities and plans for 2024, 2025, 2026 and beyond.

Following links were shared during the presentation:

- Greater Manchester Transport Strategy:
<https://tfgm.com/strategy>
- Digital Local Roads (2022):
<https://tff.uk.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/OS-Digital-Local-Roads-2022-v3.1.pdf>

2.2.3 Interactive sessions including polls, discussion, and Q&A

The Webinar included many interactive sessions which involved polls, discussion, and Questions and Answers (Q&A) sessions. There were two polls, one each presented before and after the presentation session. The first poll presented a general overview of topics the attendees related the term 'Network and Traffic Management' with. This included 'congestion', 'traffic lights', 'optimisation', 'coordination', and more based on the figure below.

What words come to your mind when you come across the term 'Network and Traffic Management'?

35 responses

Figure 2: Extract from the first poll using the Mentimeter platform

The second poll was focused on the possible topics for the future Webinar in the four-part series, which the attendees would like to see covered. The poll was shared after the presentation session and included responses such as 'Data spaces', 'Optimisation tools', 'Data quality', 'Evaluation' and more based on the figure below.

What are the topics you would like to see covered in our next TANGENT Webinar series?

11 responses

Data spaces	Evaluation	Integrated planning
Data quality	placemakingbus interventions for different scenarios	Challenges encountered and how have they been overcome.
Challenges	Optimisation tools	What's next?
Competence nerds	Competence needs	

Figure 3: Extract from the second poll using the Mentimeter platform.

In relation to the discussion and Q&A, following the first presentation, Laura was asked as she is coordinating activities with different actors, what challenges she came across in coordination between the local, national, and even international actors in the Network and Traffic Management. Laura responded that the biggest challenge for a long time was that there was no focus on the urban level at all. This is what has been changing in the past few years with the new revision in the RTTI and the National Access Points (NAP) that were set by the NAPCORE project. Besides that, there's also a little problem in the deployment and the follow-up in the projects that we have in traffic management, where there are a lot of things being tested but the implementation in later stages is dragging. It is advancing, but not at a pace that which the EU would want. Sometimes there is also a lack of national framework support, and it is a challenge at times for smaller municipalities as the larger ones usually have more

resources. The lack of support for small municipalities nationally or even regionally, can be a big challenge.

Following the second presentation, Hannah was asked if she could elaborate a bit more on the role of predictive technology and artificial intelligence (AI), in traffic management at the city level. Hannah responded that they have done a project recently, an R&D project that involves utilising AI and machine learning for adaptive signal control. This involves the deployment of video analytic sensors, so to count and classify on the network, at a signal junction. With the count and classification information, which is fed into the signal control algorithm, they were able to adapt the signals based on the policy levers. For instance, to provide priority for buses, and pedestrians (when there's a high volume of pedestrians) near stadiums or event locations, the information assists us in doing that. It is a research project, and we are looking forward to building on that. In terms of predictive capability, that's something they are looking into as well by using AIMSUN for modelling capacity in-house with TfGM. AIMSUN live gives us the real-time model, allowing them to be more reactive, see what's happening in real-time in terms of modelling and see how they can change and adapt their signal strategies, their signal control, impacts of road closures in real-time and it is an aspiration to link that into their ITS platform and their kind of network management systems.

Another question, focusing on the accuracy of quantification devices for sustainable modes like walking and cycling, was asked to Hannah by one of the Webinar attendees. They wanted to know if a certain confidence factor was maintained in the data before feeding it to UTC. To this Hannah responded by saying that they have done assessments on that quality of data and that is something they have considered over the years with network management because before feeding the information out to the customers, they need to make sure it is quality data. They have a network of Bluetooth sensors for journey time information. Now, they haven't used that for any traffic management interventions because they're not 100% sure about the accuracy and granularity of the data. Hence, they are looking at alternative data sources, and it is something that is considered. Focusing on the confidence factors and reliability, she could provide links later to the actual sensing technology for the smart junction project.

2.3 Webinar 2: Real-Time Traffic Modelling and Forecasting Tools

2.3.1 Welcome and agenda

Lakshya Pandit from Rupprecht Consult welcomed the Webinar attendees kickstarting the second TANGENT Webinar in the four-part series. Prior information regarding the technical logistics during the Webinar was given to the attendees, followed by an introduction to the TANGENT project. He later shared the goals and agenda of the Webinar, followed by the introduction of the two speakers i.e., Ynte Vanderhoydonc from IMEC and Athina Tympakianaki from AIMSUN.

Time	Description	Speaker
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome and Introduction Agenda, Aim, Speakers, TANGENT project, Technical guidance	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)
	Poll 1	
14:10 - 14:25	Presentation 1: Forecasting tools, data quality and supply prediction	Ynte Vanderhoydonc (IMEC)

Time	Description	Speaker
14:25 - 14:30	Questions and Answers for Presentation 1	
14:30 - 14:45	Presentation 2: Framework for real-time traffic management and developments on demand estimation / prediction	Athina Tympakianaki (AIMSUN)
14:45 - 14:50	Questions and Answers for Presentation 2	
14:50 - 15:00	Poll 2	
	Concluding remarks and next activities TANGENT Webinar Series and Forum	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)

Table 3: Webinar 2 Agenda

2.3.2 Presentation session

2.3.2.1 Forecasting tools, data quality and supply prediction

Ynte Vanderhoydonc from IMEC, a TANGENT partner, presented her topic for the first presentation titled 'Forecasting Tools, Data Quality, and Supply Prediction'. The presentation focused on forecasting traffic supply within the TANGENT projects and data-driven decision-making. The introductory session focused on forecasting traffic supply for short-term decision-making, which includes travel speeds, travel time, and the flow of traffic on the network. Depending on the scope of the application, different approaches were shared that should be taken into consideration. Within the local and network-wide context, local predictions focus on the locations with measurements, and this is done via data-driven approaches. On the other hand, network-wide predictions correspond to predictions on road sections of the entire road network. This is where a simulation-based model comes into play.

With the rise of data collection and data learning algorithms, it was shared how data-driven approaches capture the features present in the traffic data and use them to predict traffic state. For this, a preferred prerequisite is the availability of historical data of 1 year to capture all seasonal effects (a minimum of 2-3 months at the least). Following this, some examples of data that were worked with within the TANGENT project were shared. These included different datasets such as counts and speed from the loop detectors, journey times from the Bluetooth sensors, and floating bus data from GPS trajectories (as in the case of Manchester). More examples were also available for other case studies like Athens, Rennes, and Lisbon, besides Greater Manchester.

Following this, requirements to build a predictive deep learning model and its basis were shared by Ynte. The need for a historical dataset (e.g., speeds, flows) was stressed upon as historical observations are used to learn traffic patterns to predict future traffic conditions. This is followed by data on external features (e.g., weather, road information) and current values to predict in real-time and for short-term decision-making. In summary, current values together with data on past values are to be utilized as inputs into the deep learning model. The deep learning model consists of two parts. This includes temporal forecasting, which consists of forecasting future values of traffic state, and spatial aggregation, which represents the task of aggregating data from neighbouring locations for the location

of interest. This results in the overall time series prediction (e.g., speeds, flows) for the next 5 minutes, 10 minutes, for up to, for example, 1 hour ahead in time, which also depends upon the time stamps of the input itself.

To analyse connected data, Ynte shared how graph models were one of the most potent approaches as their mathematical calculations are specifically built to operate on relationships. An example from Manchester was shared as a visualisation. For TANGENT, different state-of-the-art methods were benchmarked, i.e., multiple methods were applied to the same datasets (both on literature datasets to link them with research and to datasets from different case studies). As an example, the mean absolute error (MAE) and average training time were shared through graphs. MAE represented the average of the absolute differences between the predictions and the observations. On the other hand, the training time is important to consider time-consuming training processes. Two methods were decided to continue with following the observations. These included MTGNN, i.e., multivariate time series forecasting with graph neural networks, and GraphConv, which is a patented code of IMEC and is strong in transfer learning, which was required to test as well for its generalizability. This meant that the model was trained on one dataset, and the model was used on a dataset in another city without training it specifically for that city (i.e., without training it on the historical data of that city). This showed promising results and was suggested as a research approach. The references to all these methods were shared towards the end of the presentation.

Considering data, data issues were the next topic of the presentation. This relates to data unavailability, data quality, missing values (for example, it can be caused by a malfunction of a recording device), and data containing noise which corresponds to extreme fluctuations and more. These are to be dealt with while considering the deep learning models. The ability of the model to predict without the incoming data was shared through the example of Greater Manchester via speeds and counts through data fusion for different forecasting periods. Following this, the requirement of denoising was also focused upon as datasets can contain a lot of noise. A comparison of predictions with and without denoising was shared for the journey times in Greater Manchester, showing how denoising captured the traffic patterns more clearly. As another example, tackling missing trajectories or lack of an identification for each distinct journey from Rennes was shared. The steps included identifying individual journeys, making a grid (to make trajectory datasets applicable to the model), calculating journey times, resampling, following which forecasting model is trained leading to route travel time predictions.

Considering anomaly detection within TANGENT, Ynte shared that non-recurrent congestions (caused by accidents or roadworks) were taken into consideration. Recurrent congestions (such as morning/evening peak hour congestion) were not considered as they are present in regular traffic patterns. For anomaly detection, identification of location and duration was also a factor which was considered.

For the congestion duration modelling, three different survival analysis models were tested, and the variables were tested for the selection of the most relevant features. These include the number of lanes for road network geometry, volume for current traffic conditions, and on-and-off-peak for the time of the day. This led to the output as a survival curve. To evaluate a correlation between the real and predicted duration times, the concordance index (i.e., c-index) was utilised. A congestion duration modelling applied on Athens' case study was shared during the presentation.

In the concluding part of the presentation, Ynte summarised the main findings and future research directions. These included benchmarking the supply forecasting results on both literature and real-world datasets. To enable real-time application to different case studies, it is important to identify the

requirements for working with different types of data. Additionally, it is crucial to focus on the necessities about denoising and resampling. For future research, major research focus areas include data preprocessing in real-time production environments and transfer learning, i.e., focusing on ways other cities can learn from already developed models.

2.3.2.2 Framework for real-time traffic management and developments on demand estimation/prediction

Athina Tympakianaki from AIMSUN, a TANGENT partner, presented 'Framework for Real-time Traffic Management and Developments in Demand Estimation/Prediction'. Athina shared the key objectives, which included providing accurate and timely information to traffic operators for proactive real-time traffic management and combining data-driven and simulation-based approaches for enhanced and more efficient solutions.

The overview of the proposed framework was shared with the Webinar participants, which was composed of two main parts: demand and supply. The supply section included data-driven models (which were presented by Ynte) that were able to predict locally the traffic conditions in the network of interest. However, these models relied on available measurements by the detectors. To predict the traffic situations for the whole network, a move towards simulation tools would be required that are able to assess the traffic situation at the whole network but can also be utilised to evaluate traffic management strategies, response plans, and incorporate information from detected events and their duration from data-driven models. One of the key inputs for the simulation models is the demand. Knowing the demand for a network of interest is important as it helps understand the mobility patterns which help to make and take decisions to prove network performance. Estimating the demand for a network was challenging (for transport managers, transport modellers, and even researchers) as within the TM context, having representative demands for a given day a database with demand matrices (Origin Destination (O/D) matrices) is required. The common practice includes extracting historical traffic measurements that are available, to apply different techniques to estimate different demands offline. Following this, depending on the real-time context, the identification of demand available (that fits prevailing traffic conditions) can be made possible.

Another problem included demand prediction, i.e., real-time demand prediction (needed to adapt the current base demand to the real-time conditions). An adapted demand would assist in providing accurate route guidance given the prevailing traffic conditions. The main challenges for demand estimation and prediction included limited observability of O/D flows, as it is difficult to know individual origins, destinations, choice of modes, and departure times. For this reason, simulation-based optimization techniques are used to infer those O/D flows using available historical traffic measurements. In addition, usually cities have their travel planning models that can provide demand for 24 hours. The static nature of the historical demand not capturing the dynamic profile also creates a barrier.

Athina reflected on how, within the TANGENT project, these limitations have been tackled by using state-of-the-art simulation-based adjustments replacing simulation-based models with data-driven machine-learning models. These models can approximate traffic/mobility behaviour (which requires data and good regularisation). The objective of this demand estimation approach is two-fold. First is to have a method that can estimate time-sliced demand that reproduces flows that we observe in real life and to also estimate the route choice simultaneously. The method is capable of being generalizable throughout the network, computationally fast, and requires little fine-tuning and simple geometry. For this approach, the data utilised includes flow counts (<10% of the sections), a flat base demand matrix (from GSM or GPS traces), with FCD (i.e., floating car data) speed and turn rates being optional.

Following this, Athina explained the problem of modelling for demand estimation through network geometry, route choice, demand, travel time, and traffic flow. The results from the Bergen network in

Norway and preliminary results from Greater Manchester i.e. TANGENT case study area were shared. For Greater Manchester, 1 month of historical data was used.

Considering demand prediction, Athina mentioned that state-of-the-art graph neural networks (MTGNNs) and spatial-temporal graph attention architecture were used. Following this, with respect to the application of this method in the TANGENT, the workflow for the case study in Athens was presented showing the input, process, output, and requirements for training a demand prediction model. This was followed by results from the test network with a total demand of approximately 232,000 trips. The simulation predictions for the Athens case study were shown for two different conditions i.e. a normal day traffic flow and a day of an event (i.e. heavy rainfall) traffic flow. Locations were identified, from the data-driven models, as anomalies. These road sections were closed due to the rainfall. Prior to the simulation of the event day, the supply in the network was modified to represent the disturbance. Similarly, differences in the traffic speeds were shared for the normal day and the event day in the different sections of the network.

In the end, Athina shared the focus of future work with enhancements in demand estimation and real-time demand prediction. Considering the demand estimation enhancements, these included scalability issues, improvement of travel-time functions, full-automation, improvement in graph representation based on turns and not sections, and comparison/validation with simulation. Considering real-time demand prediction enhancements, it was stressed how a large amount of data is needed for multiple days and time periods. Athina concluded her presentation with the references used within the project.

The following link was shared during the presentation with the Webinar participants:

- Link to Aimsun's solution portfolio where their role of data and simulation is described: <https://www.aimsun.com/aimsun-insight/>

2.3.3 Interactive sessions including polls, discussion, and Q&A

The Webinar included many interactive sessions which involved polls, discussion, and Questions and Answers (Q&A) sessions. There were two polls, one each presented before and after the presentation session. The first poll focused on tools/methodologies the Webinar participants were familiar with about real-time traffic modelling and forecasting. The results included 'Aimsun Live', 'VISSIM', 'VISUM', 'SUMO', 'time series', 'data-driven approaches', and more (as seen in Figure below).

model is then applied to the last observations (e.g., the last hour of data to predict the next hour). The last question was focused on the Greater Manchester case study. The question was 'if the motorway network was also considered for modelling?' and 'if the morning and evening peak hours changed post-COVID (corresponding to more people working from home resulting in less travel)?'. Ynte responded that the data they trained on was from 2022 and onwards, and therefore the COVID period was not taken into consideration.

Following the second presentation, Athina was asked to consider the approach of using data-driven ML model over simulation models for demand estimation, the major advantages and/or disadvantages identified and if there were circumstances that favoured simulation models over data-driven ML model approach. To this, Athina responded first with the advantages of the data-driven methods as these models are simple to use and require minimal fine-tuning as the optimization methods that have been used in tackling the demand estimation problem (depending upon the approach chosen) can be a tedious process. On the other hand, assuming the model is very well calibrated, the simulation models can capture the interaction between the demand and the supply. This includes the potential route choices, and signalised intersections where the geometry is much more detailed. The advantage of the model used in Greater Manchester was shared where only one hour of demand was calibrated, and a 24-hour profiled demand estimation was made possible.

2.4 Webinar 3: Transport Network Optimisation and Arbitration Models

2.4.1 Welcome and agenda

Lakshya Pandit from Rupprecht Consult welcomed the Webinar attendees kickstarting the third TANGENT Webinar in the four-part series. Prior information about the technical logistics during the Webinar was given to the attendees, followed by an introduction to the TANGENT project. He later shared the goals and agenda of the Webinar, followed by the introduction of the two speakers i.e., Arka Ghosh from DEUSTO and Marios Giouroukelis from NTUA.

Time	Description	Speaker
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome and Introduction Agenda, Aim, Speakers, TANGENT project, Technical guidance	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)
	Poll 1	
14:10 - 14:25	Presentation 1: Transport network optimisation problems and techniques	Dr. Arka Ghosh (DEUSTO)
14:25 - 14:30	Questions and Answers for Presentation 1	
14:30 - 14:45	Presentation 2: Development of arbitration models	Marios Giouroukelis (NTUA)
14:45 - 14:50	Questions and Answers for Presentation 2	
14:50 - 15:00	Poll 2	

Time	Description	Speaker
	Concluding remarks and next activities TANGENT Webinar Series and Forum	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)

Table 4: Webinar 3 Agenda

2.4.2 Presentation session

2.4.2.1 Forecasting tools, data quality and supply prediction

Arka Ghosh from DEUSTO, a TANGENT partner, presented his topic for the first presentation titled ‘Transport network optimisation problems and techniques’. The presentation focused on different modalities of optimisation problems that apply to transport network management. It was stressed how the generation of traffic policy and response plans have become difficult due to the multimodal nature of travel. This involves diverse stakeholders involved in transport network management making the execution of decision-making complex. Public authorities must orchestrate both current and future transport modes to manage multimodal traffic and this reflects upon the need for new tools that support decision makers. The approach taken within the TANGENT project is the use of Computer Optimised Design (COD) to generate transport policies and/or intervention to support traffic management. All the methodologies are based on AI and transport modelling consensus reaching mechanisms.

For the optimisation problem, two main use cases were presented i.e. Integration of demand responsive transport and transit modes, and synchronisation of public transport and traffic control. In relation to the integration of demand responsive transport and transit modes the term ‘optimisation’ refers to choosing the best available option to do a task that maximises the gain. In TANGENT, COD is applied to determine the optimal or near-optimal DRT fleet and operational routes to serve the first/last-mile of an area. This includes performance indicators such as percentage of demand served, total emissions produced by DRT fleet, operational costs of the DRT service, and average travel time for the passengers (first mile + public transport (PT) trip + last mile).

Figure 6: Athens case study testing connection between Thracomakedones region and the First District of Athens (Source: OpenStreetMap)

The DRT-integration methodology was tested for the Athens case study for connection between two areas as seen in the figure above. The proof-of-concept testing framework includes 200 trip requests, where the requests are randomly generated within the specified area with the start of the departure travel window being between 08:00-14:00. The problem was tested in two different settings i.e., one with 6 DRT vehicles and another with 16 vehicles. Considering the 6-vehicle setting (reflecting low operational cost), associated performance indicators were shared (e.g., demand served by DRT services including first-mile (FM) and last-mile (LM) being 28%, average passengers' travel time for PT + DRT being 76 minutes in comparison to 88 minutes for PT only). Considering the results with the 16-vehicle fleet (reflecting high served demand), the associated performance indicators showed contrasting values. The second use case of synchronisation of PT and traffic control is specific to urban scenarios where traffic lights and line-specific frequency/capacity of PT are optimised. Problems of PT were shared, which included dependence of some PT modes on traffic congestion and traffic control, and lack of flexibility to react to sudden changes in demand or supply (e.g. no sudden changes in frequency and/capacity). The TANGENT approach for this use case includes consideration of certain planned or unplanned events (e.g., failure of metro lines), the frequency and/or capacity of some surface PT lines, and traffic control plan re-adjustment. The performance indicators for this use case are user costs of the affected PT lines, operational cost of PT fleet, congestion in predefined areas, and reduction in the system-wide emission. This task was carried out for a small network near old Trafford stadium in Manchester. This was tested in Greater Manchester using the AIMSUN model including 10 PT bus lines and 24 signalised nodes (in total 81 phases were considered). Following this, the test network was presented by Arka, where KPIs and baseline scenarios in TANGENT tool was showcased. This was developed for visualisation and optimisation task (as shown below).

Figure 7: Baseline scenario through TANGENT tool with key performance indicators in Manchester

Figure 8: Optimised scenario through TANGENT tool with key performance indicators in Manchester

The proof-of-concept results for synchronisation of PT and traffic control showed how the service frequency was improved while there was reduction in the user costs (PT delay time), travel congestion (delay time by travel time), and emissions. In contrast the PT operational cost had increased due to the increase in the number of buses for the operation. Arka concluded the presentation with the preliminary study outcomes and stressed that the limit to different indicators would depend upon the stakeholder inputs in the future.

2.4.2.2 Development of arbitration models

Marios Giouroukelis from NTUA, a TANGENT partner, presented development of arbitration models focusing on the consensus mechanism. Addressing the previous presentation, Marios shared the

importance of asking stakeholders needs with respect to optimisation problems, which is then followed by opinion to direct work towards the priorities. The consensus mechanism is coupled with these optimisation problems within TANGENT. Marios shared as an introduction how transport network management is characterised by multiple decision-makers (stakeholders) with different beliefs, multiple possible network configurations and difficulty in reaching consensus-based decisions. For this the state-of-the-art consensus building tools are necessary.

Considering the consensus mechanism, the project takes consensus on the performance indicators (as discussed in the first presentation). To do so, gathering opinion is the first step. This is done through paired evaluations/preferences of different transport network objectives. These include service performance, network efficiency, economic performance, economic performance and environmental performance. In the example shared by Marios, it was observed that Environmental performance was prioritised slightly more than service performance.

Figure 9: One of the iterations during arbitration between two prominent opinions (sp = service performance, ne = network efficiency, ep = economic performance, env = environmental performance)

After the collection of opinions, the next step was shared i.e. to identify prominent opinions. With the input of data regarding stakeholder opinion for each transport management strategy, clustering of various opinions is done into 2 clusters using Fuzzy C-means clustering algorithm which results in the identification of majority and minority opinion groups. Following the identification of majority and minority opinions, the next steps focus on understanding how stakeholders communicate with one another. This included asking stakeholders to nominate possible partners and provide the nature of interactions. For instance, the patterns of exchange, the overall integrations of their organisations and other indicators. Using a data-driven method, the Bayesian network, the probability for stakeholders to communicate with other stakeholders is identified. Using this method a stakeholder graph is built for each problem i.e. when applying a particular strategy, as not all strategies are of interest for every stakeholder. This leads to different stakeholder graphs for different strategies.

Following the identification of important opinions and stakeholder graphs, Marios shared the next step of opinion exchange, where modelling of exchanges between stakeholders is done using RL in an opinion dynamic setting (to simulate opinion exchanges between stakeholders). The next step includes arbitration where the stakeholders come together to find a solution. This method includes the role of an arbitrator who invites spokespersons for each cluster to adjust their opinions and includes an iterative process based on consensus reaching process (CRP) framework. Considering the input of two prominent opinions from the previous step (as seen in the figure above), a single opinion matrix of consensual preferences is generated.

Figure 10: Objective weights for different strategies

Towards the end, Marios shared the final step in the process i.e. derivation of weights, where the objective weights from the consensual opinion matrix for each problem within TANGENT is generated. These include Signal-Vehicle Couple Control (SVCC), Synchronisation of Public Transport and Traffic Control (PT-TC Sync), Synchronisation of DRT and Transit modes (DRT-PT Sync), and Dynamic Congestion Pricing (DCP). In conclusion, a decision-support tool was created to facilitate decision-making in this context through realistic modelling of usual steps in reaching decisions (i.e. opinion exchange, arbitration, etc.). This involves state-of-the-art, data-driven models trained on actual stakeholder preferences following a modular approach. Further provision of the preference part of the preference-based optimisation approach is adopted in WP5 within the TANGENT project.

2.4.3 Interactive sessions including polls, discussion, and Q&A

The Webinar included many interactive sessions which involved polls, discussion, and Questions and Answers (Q&A) sessions. There were two polls, one each presented before and after the presentation session. The first poll aimed at gathering responses on the Webinar participant’s familiarity with traffic network optimisation and arbitration approaches for cities. Some of the participants were not familiar with the term while other responses included dynamic traffic lights, 'optimising route planning', 'reducing travel time', 'cost function', 'management of congestion', 'social benefits', and more (as seen in the figure below).

Are you familiar with traffic network optimisation and arbitration approaches for cities? If no, how do you interpret these terms? If yes, do mention.

15 responses

Figure 11: Extract from the first poll using the Mentimeter platform.

The second poll focused on the possible topics for the future Webinar in the four-part series, which the attendees would like to see covered. The poll was shared after the presentation session and included responses such as 'impacts of multimodal traffic management, traffic forecasting', 'how much optimisation can be done daily for PT and DRT dynamic synchronisation' and 'practical cases and how it works on ground'.

In the discussion and Q&A session following the first presentation, there was an exchange between the moderator and the speaker, considering synchronisation of public transport and traffic control. As an increase in PT operational costs was observed during the testing, there was a question concerning any identification of potential limit or threshold to this key indicator. For instance, if the public transport operation costs go beyond a threshold limit that makes it difficult to implement the proposed solution or if different cities indicate differences in the KPI thresholds. To this, Arka responded that the thresholds are to be defined by the stakeholder/responsible actor themselves. During the testing, there was no input from the stakeholder regarding this. In the cost function, different weights for each of the KPIs have been used. This is based on how the stakeholder wants to prioritise these operational costs, and the corresponding weight values can be used as the input values. The optimisation process will consider it as important or less important. For the current testing results, static values have been utilised. There is a provision for stakeholders, if they want to prioritise optimising operational costs rather than putting weight on the travel time (which can be done by changing/manipulating weights).

Following the second presentation, Marios was asked to consider the arbitration step where two prominent opinions are identified. The question focused on whether all stakeholders had equal weight on the opinion. To this, Marios responded that all stakeholders had equal weight. In some cases, in cities, there is also consultation with other stakeholders that usually have the power. The next steps would include the approach of a weightage being proposed based on the hierarchy of power the stakeholder has for the decision-making. Later, a follow-up question was asked considering if there is a quantitative limit to address additional objectives when identified (considering currently there are four). Marios addressed the question, by explaining how the objectives are evaluated in a pairwise comparison with stakeholders and by adding the objectives the burden for stakeholders to respond to the questions gets quite high due to added comparisons.

2.5 Webinar 4: Transport Network Optimisation and Arbitration Models

2.5.1 Welcome and agenda

Lakshya Pandit from Rupprecht Consult welcomed the Webinar attendees kickstarting the final TANGENT Webinar in the four-part series. Prior information about the technical logistics during the Webinar was given to the attendees, followed by an introduction to the TANGENT project including goals and features by Leire Serrano (DEUSTO – Project Coordinator). Following this, the agenda of the Webinar was shared, followed by the introduction of the two speakers i.e., Tiago Dias from A-to-Be and Lucie Tristant from ID4MOBILITY.

Time	Description	Speaker
14:00 - 14:20	Welcome and Introduction Agenda, Goals, Speakers, Technical guidance	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)
	TANGENT project: Goals & Features	Leire Serrano (DEUSTO)

Time	Description	Speaker
	Poll 1	
14:20 - 14:35	Presentation 1: Integrated tool for Cooperative Traffic Management	Tiago Dias (A-to-Be)
14:35 – 14:40	Questions and Answers for Presentation 1	
14:40 - 14:55	Presentation 2: Case Study Implementation	Lucie Tristant (ID4Mobility)
14:55 - 15:00	Questions and Answers for Presentation 2	
15:00 - 15:15	Poll 2	
	Concluding remarks TANGENT Webinar Series and Forum	Lakshya Pandit (RUPPRECHT)

Table 5: Webinar 4 Agenda

2.5.2 Presentation session

2.5.2.1 Integrated Tool for Cooperative Traffic Management

Tiago Dias, representing A-to-Be, provided an overview of the cooperative traffic management tool developed within the TANGENT project, emphasising its potential to streamline traffic management operations across urban areas through a modular, integrated platform. The tool aims to bring together real-time data from diverse sources such as sensors, public transport data, and floating car data, forming a unified traffic management interface for operators. Its primary objectives include enabling predictive traffic monitoring, supporting decision-making, and facilitating efficient response strategies to manage incidents effectively. Tiago explained that the tool's key features include a dashboard visualisation for real-time data, predictive traffic modelling, and a planning module that allows traffic operators to prepare for anticipated events or incidents.

Dashboard and Monitoring Functions

Tiago showcased the dashboard functionality, which allows traffic operators to access a dynamic, user-friendly interface. The dashboard displays real-time indicators such as average road speed, traffic congestion hotspots, and delays in public transportation. Users can monitor congestion levels and response actions across specified city regions. Tiago highlighted the tool's advanced customisation features, enabling operators to adapt the dashboard to specific city areas or scenarios. The dashboard's heat map, which aggregates traffic data visually, simplifies quick identification of problem areas, allowing for efficient response coordination.

Figure 12: TANGENT Dashboard as presented by Tiago Dias during the Webinar

Response and Planning Module

A standout feature discussed by Tiago was the planning and response module, which supports incident management through predefined response plans. By using simulation models, the tool predicts traffic patterns based on expected events, such as floods or major city events, allowing stakeholders to create optimised response strategies. Tiago explained that these plans include a set of actionable steps tailored to various stakeholders, including bus route adjustments and traffic light reconfiguration. The comparative response plan, for instance, fosters inter-stakeholder cooperation, ensuring that each action aligns with the priorities of different transport operators. He emphasised that the tool was designed with human oversight in mind, giving operators the final decision on implementing proposed actions rather than fully automating the process.

Data Interoperability and Adaptability

Tiago elaborated on the technical adaptability of the tool, noting that its flexible structure allows for seamless integration of various data sources. The interoperability of the tool with multiple data types and sources addresses critical aspects of modern multimodal traffic management. Operators can also customise the data sources displayed on the dashboard, focusing on specific regions or transport indicators. Tiago highlighted that the tool's modular nature makes it highly adaptable to the needs of diverse urban areas, supporting a cooperative framework that can expand to accommodate new transport data standards.

2.5.2.2 Case Study Implementation

Lucie Tristant, from ID4Mobility, presented the implementation results of the TANGENT tool in case studies. She described the collaborative testing approach adopted over six months, highlighting the importance of iterative testing to capture nuanced feedback from stakeholders on the tool's functionalities. The focus of this implementation was on evaluating three core areas: usability, accuracy of displayed data, and compliance with initial case study requirements.

Usability and User Interface

Lucie reported that users found the dashboard intuitive and easy to navigate, with high customisability enabling adaptation for different user groups, from traffic operators to strategic decision-makers. She noted that certain elements, such as public transport and incident data, required further refinement for clarity, but overall, stakeholders appreciated the ability to tailor dashboard views to specific requirements. The complexity of the dashboard, while extensive, was seen as beneficial in offering a comprehensive set of tools; however, Lucie mentioned the need for training sessions to help users become adept at managing the diverse functionalities offered by the platform.

Data Accuracy and Scenario-Based Testing

During testing, data accuracy emerged as a crucial factor, with stakeholders assessing the reliability of traffic indicators, predictive forecasts, and real-time updates. Lucie explained that the accuracy varied depending on the case study's data sources and the nature of scenarios being simulated, such as routine traffic flow or planned events like football games. In some instances, the customisability of the tool allowed users to adjust data inputs to better match local circumstances, ensuring relevance in data representation. The availability of quality, reliable data was critical, as insufficient or inconsistent data affected the tool's performance, underscoring the importance of robust data governance.

Lessons Learned and Future Plans for Case Studies

For Rennes, Lucie highlighted how TANGENT had strengthened collaborative traffic management efforts, encouraging multi-stakeholder engagements to address shared urban mobility challenges. One outcome was the establishment of a dedicated working group to discuss and enhance inter-organisation cooperation for traffic management. Future plans in Rennes also include efforts to upgrade data-sharing frameworks and leverage TANGENT's functionalities to develop a cohesive, city-wide traffic management strategy.

In Lisbon, TANGENT underscored the operational value of having an automated, centralised traffic monitoring tool. Lucie noted that the tool provided a systematic approach to data sharing and highlighted legal and technical challenges related to sensitive data management. As a future direction, Lisbon is considering adopting a standardised protocol for data collection and dissemination, ensuring that data used across platforms is both accurate and secure. TANGENT's collaborative framework has also opened up avenues for Lisbon's traffic managers to learn from other European cities, offering valuable insights for shaping future policy directions.

Lucie reported that TANGENT enhanced Greater Manchester's operational capabilities by providing real-time data and shared information among stakeholders, which allowed for faster incident response and decision-making. This efficiency was complemented by an automated data-sharing process, reducing manual communication between stakeholders and facilitating faster dissemination of key updates. For Manchester, the project demonstrated the necessity of open, accessible data to support cohesive traffic management and highlighted the potential of TANGENT to drive strategic technology adoption within the city's transport management infrastructure.

2.5.3 Interactive sessions including polls, discussion, and Q&A

The Webinar included many interactive sessions which involved polls, discussion, and Questions and Answers (Q&A) sessions. There were two polls, one each presented before and after the presentation session. The first poll aimed at gathering responses on the Webinar participant's familiarity with tools (digital/on-site) in relation to 'traffic management solutions'. The responses included traffic counters, traffic management centre/control centre rooms, floating car data, atlas, traffic sensors, variable message signages, and route advise in vehicles.

Which tools (digital/on-site) come to your mind in relation to 'traffic management solutions'?

11 responses

Figure 13: Mentimeter responses from the first poll

Through the second poll, focusing on key insights from the Webinar, the participants highlighted finding dashboard with heat map (including integration with forecasting), workflow for cooperative response plan, integration of several data sources from different environments, importance of cooperation as interesting aspects.

In the Q&A session, Tiago addressed queries on the technical aspects of road delay calculations, explaining that these are based on free-flow conditions. He also clarified the decision-support role of the tool, highlighting that it was not intended to replace human operators but rather to assist them with timely, data-driven recommendations. Tiago concluded by reiterating that the tool represents a significant advancement in urban traffic management, integrating real-time data with cooperative strategies for enhanced traffic optimisation across urban networks.

Following the second presentation, Lucie concluded by summarising the key findings across case studies, noting that TANGENT had successfully demonstrated the importance of multi-stakeholder cooperation, open and reliable data access, and a centralised traffic management tool. In the Q&A, she discussed prerequisites for future implementations, such as the availability of quality data sources and alignment with national traffic protocols. Lucie also addressed potential obstacles, such as differences in data standards across countries, and the benefits of integrating TANGENT’s functionalities as add-ons to existing traffic management systems to maximise scalability and ease of adoption.

3 Advisory Board Sessions

This chapter focuses on the role of the Advisory Board (AB) and the associated activities involving AB sessions in the TANGENT project, with identified benefits and discussions taking place in different phases of the project.

3.1 Role and benefits

The **Advisory Board** plays a crucial role in the TANGENT project by contributing to the dissemination, exploitation, and communication of the project's results. They actively identify market opportunities for the TANGENT outcomes and assist in defining new business models. Additionally, the Advisory Board provides an external and independent perspective, offering valuable feedback on the project's progress and its achieved results. Their insights and expertise enhance the project's overall impact and effectiveness.

The Advisory Board enjoys several key benefits as part of their role in the TANGENT project:

1. **Access to the TANGENT Forum:** The Advisory Board has exclusive access to a dedicated online platform—the TANGENT Forum. This platform serves as a hub for discussions, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among experts, stakeholders, and project partners. It provides a space for in-depth conversations, document sharing, and real-time updates related to the project.
2. **Networking Opportunities:** Members of the Advisory Board engage with a diverse range of stakeholders. They connect not only within the Advisory Board itself but also with participants from the broader TANGENT Forum and beyond. These networking opportunities foster cross-sectoral dialogue, enabling the exchange of ideas, best practices, and innovative solutions.
3. **Cutting-Edge Research:** The Advisory Board receives priority access to cutting-edge research on traffic operations within the Project. They stay informed about the latest advancements, methodologies, and trends in urban mobility and transportation. This knowledge equips them to provide informed feedback and strategic guidance to the project.
4. **Webinar Access:** The Advisory Board has the exclusive opportunity to participate in four webinars hosted by the TANGENT project team. These webinars delve into specific topics, share project updates, and provide a platform for interactive discussions. Board members can engage directly with experts, ask questions, and contribute their expertise.

3.2 Selection process

The Advisory Board is an advising body for solicited and unsolicited advice to TANGENT Activities about the project. The main task of the Advisory Board is to give overall non-binding strategic advice to serve the common objectives and vision of TANGENT.

This also entails the promotion of TANGENT and the dissemination of the elaborated findings within the own sectoral networks. The Advisory Board was installed as a defined group of up to 10 persons. The following criteria was applied for the selection of Advisory Board Members:

1. Representing a multi-national stakeholder group with a European interest or being a renowned expert having a known status in a relevant network; representing one or multiple key sectors such as Digitalisation, Multimodality, Sustainable Urban Mobility, Public transport, Transport modelling, Research, and Data providers (e.g., transport service provider, infrastructure operators, charging infrastructure).
2. Ability to communicate sectoral positions to TANGENT and vice-versa.
3. Availability and participation in regular meetings.

To ensure a relevant sectoral representativeness, the Advisory Board consisted of different (non-profit) associations, municipalities and regions, transport operators (public transport, last-mile, etc.), academia, representing relevant stakeholder groups like global private players, data and service providers, industry and (end-)users as well as ambassadors of flagship (data) projects which should cover relevant key domains. By involving only associations, the geographical coverage across Europe is well addressed and the risk of specific company influences is minimised. A consistent representation across the sectors is the aim for the Advisory Board.

The list of Advisory Board Members was managed by TANGENT Project Coordinator, DEUSTO. In case some members are not contributing on a regular basis, they were excluded, whilst new members were included in the Advisory Board. Following the GDPR, the names of the AB Members are not disclosed in this report.

3.3 Timeline and sessions

AB sessions were carried during the TANGENT project's timeline as follows:

Date	AB Session	Format	AB Members / Participants
10.02.2023	First Advisory Board Meeting	Digital	10 / 25
22.06.2023	AB Session 1: Advancing Mode Choice Predictions: Exploring State-of-the-Art Methods and Emerging Data Sources	Digital	4 / 13
23.06.2023	AB Session 2: Advancing Mobility Strategies: State-of-the-Art Traffic Forecasting and Generation of Transport Policy and Response Plans Using Automatic Design Concept	Digital	6 / 17
26.06.2023	AB Session 3: Unlocking Data Collaboration and Assessing Smart Infrastructure Indexes	Digital	5 / 15
01.12.2023	AB Session 4: Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting: Supply Forecasting and Anomaly Detection Outputs	Digital	5 / 17
01.12.2023	AB Session 5: Initial results obtained testing individual components + Modelling of Stakeholder opinions and the formation of consensus	Digital	5 / 17
01.12.2023	AB Session 6: Update on Case Studies including current challenges in implementation + First preliminary results	Digital	5 / 17

Date	AB Session	Format	AB Members / Participants
16.10.2024	Future of TANGENT Tools: Lessons and Recommendations	Hybrid	AB Members: 3 Overall participants: 33 In-person / 17 online

Table 6: AB Sessions and Format in TANGENT

3.3.1 First Advisory Board Meeting

Morgane Juliat from Rupprecht Consult received the participants with a welcome speech, introducing the meeting core team, following up with an introduction round, where the esteemed members of the Advisory Board, introduced themselves, participating simultaneously in a Miro exercise, citing their experience and expertise. A short exercise round using the Miro board was performed where the members of the Advisory Board also highlighted their expectations from the project and the meeting. Morgane Juliat went through the agenda, explaining shortly the purpose of the meeting and the output desired from the discussion with the members of the Board. Leire Serrano, Project Coordinator of TANGENT, then introduced the project to the members, vividly describing the goal, status of the tasks, methodology, and expected outcome of the project.

The project overview was followed by a short description of the services undertaken in the project, to implement the tools of the project, by Antonio Masegosa from Deusto. Each service was planned to be followed by a Miro exercise where feedback and comments from the Board were to be gathered. But due to time constraints and the prioritisation of discussions to take place, the exercise for Service 1 could only be undertaken together with discussions with the members for Service 1 and 2.

Discussion about Service 1 invited an interesting exchange of thoughts and explanations from the Advisory Board and our partners. Some of the questions from the Advisory Members were noted as follows: Which minimal data are requested to have the desired quality output? What business model does this Project TANGENT have in sight?

Antonio (Deusto), from the project's point of view, considered data like good coverage, and traffic counters in the city to be important whereas Eleni (NTUA) opined that the path of minimum approach was also considered. She also stated that during the development of the services, problems with some kind of specific data occurred as the issue of public and private governance is still to be sorted out. Antonio also stated that through service 2 and service 3, the project also analysed the direct or indirect impacts of the peak events.

Focusing on the discussion about Service 2 functionality "Common Operational Picture", the feedback obtained are listed below:

2 AB Members opined that the information about the simulation model and the prediction model could also influence the Service Contracts of the different public operators of the cities. So, the time responses, and flexible tools that are needed for public transport should also be considered. The problem of understanding how the public transport works should be resolved on the first step because the frequency of the service and the number of drivers present in the system are already fixed so a change or introduction of a new policy would not fit well into the system easily and steps should be taken first to consider these problems. Further feedback focused on the coordination and flexibility from

the cities and the departments, as it should be there to consider and implement the TANGENT services as the project proposes new tools for finding specific solutions. These solutions and tools should be encouraged to be implemented so that the impacts could be analysed, and the parameters needed to be modified in the transport systems could also be evaluated.

Leire (Deusto) from the Project's point of view, asserted that TANGENT is catering to develop new tools and solutions to find answers to some specific problems, existing in the transport system of the participating cities, by implementing innovative services in the cities, as a demand from the European Commission, engaging different actors and stakeholders in delivering the optimum solution, improving coordination, developing suitable indicators for better efficiency and operation.

Towards the end of the meeting, AB Members were notified that they would be invited to the TANGENT Forum in coming weeks before the next AB session.

3.3.2 AB Session 1: Advancing Mode Choice Predictions: Exploring State-of-the-Art Methods and Emerging Data Sources

Morgane Juliat from Rupprecht Consult received the participants with a welcome speech, describing the goals and agenda of the meeting and the expectation from the AB members. Marios Giouroukelis from NTUA started with a brief overview of work package 3: Mode Choice models explaining its objectives in detail to the participants. The objectives include a) Factors affecting travel decision-making, b) Models to describe travel choices, c) Identification of behavioural shifts and d) Recommendations for developing and incorporating behavioural models. Also discussed were factors affecting travel decision-making and based on these factors developing a set of models to describe those choices and preferences about data collection strategies. Next discussed were the contents and scenarios of the Stated Preferences Survey developed to introduce new services and implementation of new strategies synchronising public transport with new functionalities. Marios then elaborated on the model development from the above-mentioned survey and explained the pros and cons of the Travel choice models illustrating a result of a multinomial logit model. Followed to this was the discussion round involving the AB members.

The topics of the discussion as shown in the figure below included mode choice modelling, new data sources and new modes.

Discussion Topics

- **Theme A: Who is interested in mode choice modeling?**
 - From research to industry applications
 - Potential users of mode choice models
- **Theme B: New data**
 - Beyond surveys: new data sources
 - Prominent open databases
 - What would it take for the industry to share its data?
 - A possible quid -pro-quo (?): Transport modelling for transport data
- **Theme C: New modes**
 - Evidence of change in mode choice after the introduction of novel mobility options.

Figure 14: Extract from WP3 presentation of the meeting, highlighting the topics for the discussion

The issues or queries concerning the above-mentioned topics that were discussed are listed below:

- Problems arising in mode choice modelling
- Sharing of data
- Difficulties in Collecting Data
- New mode choices

An AB member suggested that mode choice is particularly helpful when performed in a dynamic way to analyse disruptions or mode change for a particular incident. Another AB member discussed how the project Orchestra is focussing on the mode choice modelling on dealing with disruptions and capacity reduction to manage traffic more effectively. Rescheduling transport, rerouting traffic, coordination, alternative mode choices and information exchange are some of the options that the project is looking into rather than passenger flows to provide better service to the passengers. They also opined that collecting reliable and relevant data is necessary for smart traffic management and a well-synchronised public transport. They also suggested that travel support and service providers can benefit from information and support from those that are doing traffic management. They suggested that information about journeys and other relevant data are to some extent essential within road transport in the future to facilitate the smart management of the traffic and also facilitate the planning of public transport and other transport services.

Another AB member also complemented this viewpoint, suggesting that data should be collected from unbiased sources, making it more transparent and acceptable. They also suggested that better-shared mobility and accessible public transport led to a better qualitative approach making it more attractive and flexible and should be included in business models of cities.

Another opinion was on the mode choice being an essential tool to analyse mobility behaviour and predict the mode choices of passengers. Stakeholders of a city should also participate more in analysing this and the tools from this project could be used to do that. The AB member also suggested reliable data could be made available from public authorities in the form of a directive to make things simpler and more efficient.

Towards the end of the session, AB Members were notified of the upcoming activities including AB session and Webinars.

3.3.3 AB Session 2: Advancing Mobility Strategies: State-of-the-Art Traffic Forecasting and Generation of Transport Policy and Response Plans Using Automatic Design Concept

Morgane Juliat from Rupprecht Consult received the participants with a welcome speech, describing the goals and agenda of the meeting and the expectation from the AB members. Antonio Masegosa from DEUSTO started the agenda by explaining the Generation of Transport Policy and Response Plans using Computer Optimised Design (COD) as a part of WP5. This included the major challenges in transport and the need to orchestrate current and future transport modes providing new tools to the decision-makers.

Following this was the illustration of the different computer-optimised designs to be developed in the project. Marios Giouroukelis from NTUA provided inputs about the Consensus Mechanism and how the preference matrices will be used. Following was the presentation about the topic of Dynamic Congestion Pricing and how it will be developed in TANGENT to analyse different performance indicators.

Further discussed was the approach of TANGENT in the Integration of Demand Responsive Transport and transit modes with the aspects of first mile/last mile problem, DRT as a feeder to PT using performance indicators. The next topic was TANGENT's approach to considering various performance indicators in the synchronisation of public transport in case of planned or unplanned events. Another topic of presentation was TANGENT's approach to applying COD to optimise path assignment for the complete CAV fleet and the traffic control plan of the network. Corresponding Performance indicators to reach this goal were also discussed. Athina Tympakianaki from Aimsun and Ngoc Quang Luon from IMEC continued the second session of the meeting with WP4 of the project focussing on Transport prediction and Simulation Models. The work package aims to create a framework architecture within the project to analyse the interoperability of demand and supply models using simulation. It described how the framework is created with OD matrices, data collection and preparation for demand & supply and the workflow of it to predict and analyse the congestion.

Considering the feedback from the AB members, the first round of discussion on the topic of Dynamic congestion pricing (DCP) as a part of WP5. The discussion was started by an AB Member citing a cost restriction to the scheme which was seconded by another member about how the dynamicity of DCP should be controlled. Further additions were on how diverse types of mobility could be added as indicators for DCP. It was suggested that DCP leads to an increase in mobility because people travel more. As a result, it must be implemented properly but the main factor is the pricing combined with societal acceptance of this measure. Another AB member opined that another indicator, to optimise transport, could be to reduce public transport fares and increase the toll if necessary.

The second round of discussion, considering feedback from AB Members, was on the aspect of the Integration of DRT and transit modes. The discussion was started by citing safety and accessibility to be considered especially for older and disabled people. An AB member vouched for intermodality linking public transport with rural areas as it could be integrated into DRT. Athina from Aimsun commented that it is also noteworthy to analyse emissions from DRT separating normal vehicle fleets and electric vehicle fleets.

Another topic of discussion was based on the queries/issues of PT and traffic control. An AB member started the discussion by recommending indicators like emissions and cost to be included as performance indicators. They also suggested the inclusion of catastrophic events like big touristic events to be included under scenario consideration. On being asked about the methods of adjusting traffic plans by the AB member, it was explained by Antonio from Deusto that adjustments like changes in frequencies, phase adjustments, and changes in time are the options that are being considered. The next round of discussion was based on an approach to apply COD to optimise path assignment for the

complete CAV fleet and the traffic control plan of the network. AN AB member opined that controlling CAVs might not be a feasible option as they would be controlled by manufacturers.

The second session of the discussion round concerning WP4 saw the AB members being asked issues about the Supply Forecasting Methodology. The first question was raised by an AB member about the property of the Mean Absolute Error for the speed and whether it shows fluctuating characteristics at different time spans and also whether the 12h forecasting window could be reduced to a lower value to represent more closely morning and afternoon peak hours so that traffic fluctuations are analysed more efficiently. Mahdi Rahimiasl from IMEC, a member of WP4 opined that the error increases when the prediction horizon increases. Also, models show better accuracy for a 12-time period compared to individual hours, and it is most suited for model optimisation.

The next query raised from the consortium towards the AB was whether the granularity of predictive indicators like average count and speed should be lowered concerning vehicles for better traffic management analyses. According to an AB member, granularity is subjective to the measures that are to be analysed for the traffic management parameters for e.g., lower values suit more to individual vehicle property better whereas higher count is more suited for properties about the entire network.

With regards to the transport model and governance as a continuation of the AB Meeting from 22.6.2023, an AB member explained the unpredictability of human behaviour and understanding and how it influences the transport model even with state-of-the-art road networks, known traffic flow etc. Also, the governance of cities on transport infrastructure should base on the simulation model to have a homogenous transport model. Also suggested was that small European cities should try to implement these easy innovative traffic solutions and discuss the results for betterment. They also opined that the TANGENT project should bring in proposals which are market comparable.

3.3.4 AB Session 3: Unlocking Data Collaboration and Assessing Smart Infrastructure Indexes

Morgane Juliat from Rupprecht Consult received the participants with a welcome speech, describing the goals and agenda of the meeting and the expectation from the AB members. During the presentation session, Marco Comerio from CEFRIEL started with a brief overview of the topic of Fostering a data-sharing culture starting on the subject of Data collection and harmonisation, using a tool to develop new services and solutions for traffic management in the project TANGENT. The different sources of data needed to optimise operations in traffic management and harmonisation of data were also discussed. The tasks executed under the umbrella of WP2 of the project about the elicitation, definition and development of the data under the realm of the Data Catalogue developed in the project were also discussed. Next discussed were the different barriers in Data sharing in terms of organisational and technical scope and it was followed by a Miro board exercise to gather inputs from the AB members on the same topic.

Next on the agenda was Smart Infrastructure Classification discussed by Ana V. Silva and Tiago Dias from A-to-Be as a part of WP6 of the project. They shared the screen discussing in detail the Automated Driving Context Domains including SAE levels, Road Readiness Automation, Physical and Digital Road Infrastructure, ISAD Index etc. Further discussed was how the project developed its integrated framework for supporting transport, operational management and strategic decision making where different transport data sets, AI techniques, analytical models and simulation tools are integrated to provide real-time and forecast in dashboards to different stakeholders. This was followed by an open discussion round engaging the AB members to participate in brainstorming about the potential relevance and adequacy of this segment.

The first interactive discussion round using a Miro board about the first topic in the agenda aimed at identifying barriers to the need for data sharing, prioritising those barriers through a voting process to filter the important barriers and then suggesting strategies and solutions to overcome those. The three

most preferred data barriers included data governance being not clearly defined, data quality (and liability) and usability of data being low due to licences, quality, completeness, etc. Many different solutions to data sharing barriers were discussed ranging from standardising mechanisms, data quality metrics, ensuring documentation etc. and how they should be followed and executed.

For data governance, strategies and solutions included implementation of data governance training for the organisations, standardising data governance mechanisms and categories, utilising blockchain technology to provide different views of data, and each region having different governance models that work, promoting EU wide discussions at regional level. For data quality, strategies and solutions included standardisation, having a professional entity to manage data and the quality, having data quality metrics and data audits, using rules like defining measurement units etc. not part of the standards, and creating a data quality index defining minimums. For usability of data, strategies and solutions to overcome the barriers included using common licences, providing metadata about completeness, licence, etc., ensuring that documentation and examples are provided.

Discussion of the second agenda topic, i.e. Smart Infrastructure Classification, was elaborated in detail by the AB Members and consortium partners about the pros and cons of classification in infrastructure and road. Also discussed were the changes needed in traffic management to accommodate communicating automated vehicles for better optimisation of transport infrastructure. The primary topic of discussion as evident from the figure below was brainstorming about the relevancy of classifying Infrastructures for facilitating automated driving behaviour and digitally monitored mobility or classification of roads should be the main priority involving automation levels, Level of Service etc. concerning the viewpoint of mobility planners.

The main issue concerning relevancy of classification systems is stated below:

- Focus on specific types of Road usage like automated driving.
- Whether it should be looked at in a broader sense thinking it of as a connected and digital framework where mobility flows

With regards to this, it was stated by an AB member that classifying infrastructure to provide safety and security to the vehicle does not provide any advantage when the vehicle does not want to use it or wants to be fully integrated rather it should be about systems controlled by the vehicles as discussed at the United Nations level. They also opined that the Level of Service provided by the infrastructure depends on the vehicles and not on the category of automation. Tiago Dias from A-to-Be enquired whether infrastructure should limit the vehicles from moving and have the possibility of controlling the vehicles from an OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer) perspective. It was suggested by the AB member that the correlation between infrastructure and the vehicles might not be the right approach as different systems of vehicles could be available from the manufacturers.

Open issues for Discussion

Classification schemes

Q1. Relevancy of Classification systems?

- Classification of **Infrastructures** alone?
 - for Automated Driving in particular
 - for a Connected and Digitally monitored Mobility
- Classification of **Roads as systems?**
(combining Infrastructure characterization, Vehicles automation levels, Levels of Service for AD, etc)

Q2. Adequacy of the ISAD index

- For urban/peri-urban roads?
- Which characteristics are missing?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 955273

TANGENT

Figure 15: Extract from project presentation for the meeting

Another AB member, on the other hand, suggested that this classification is comparable with the service level in the telecom network. As automated vehicle states don't interact with the infrastructure and the traffic management and they are autonomous, traffic management should also influence the operation of the vehicles in the network and a corresponding level of service should be provided so that at different roads they could adapt themselves to the service level. They opined that this classification could be a necessity in the future as the vehicles are not adapted nowadays to communicate with traffic management.

To add more about vehicle connectivity, an AB member opined that although there is ADAS and Level 4 automation available today, many times they are not connected to the public infrastructure or the C-ITS infrastructure of the city creating disruptions during driving. Also, manufacturers create their network separate from old-fashioned C-ITS creating more hindrances.

Ana V. Silva suggested that the focus should also be on authorities and how they want to control the city and how can classification systems developed in this project could help them understand which parts of the city are more ready to be controlled and monitored and these systems could be classified as framework helping in building up of these in the infrastructure. It was also discussed that the quality and signage of roads should also be improved or made effective for the smooth operations of automated vehicles.

An AB Member also opined that creating a sound transport infrastructure is very much dependent on the government because of the practical implementation of these systems. Performance indicators should be feasible to bring about the potential change. They also shared the following links to the meeting participants:

- https://cms.uitp.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Project-Brief-SPACE_OCT12021.pdf
- <https://cms.uitp.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Annexe.pdf>

3.3.5 AB Session 4: Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting: Supply Forecasting and Anomaly Detection Outputs

The three AB Sessions (Session 4, 5 and 6) were held online on the same day with the agenda items and presentations shared prior to the meeting with the AB Members for better flow of discussions. Lakshya Pandit from Rupprecht Consult welcomed the Advisory Board Members and the project partners kickstarting the Advisory Board Meeting. Information relating to the technical logistics during the AB Meeting was given to the members. The goals and the agenda of the Advisory Board Meeting were later shared, followed by a brief overview of the TANGENT Services and Functionalities (as seen in the image below) by Antonio David Masegosa from DEUSTO. This was followed by presentations from project partners focusing on technical work packages.

Figure 16: Flowchart of TANGENT Services and corresponding Functionalities

Ynte Vanderhoydonc from IMEC and Athina Tympakianaki from AIMSUN gave the first presentation of the session. Athina introduced the real-time traffic management framework (see figure below) which they are developing within TANGENT. The scope of the framework was to connect different components with respect to predicting the supply. The framework consists of two components i.e., demand and supply, which receives historical data (time series of flows, speeds etc.) from multiple days. The supply component includes developing methods that are based on machine learning techniques that are data driven.

Athina shared a scenario where once an incident is detected and its duration has been predicted, supply modifications can be applied in the simulation network accordingly. For instance, in case of an accident where a lane or a whole road section needs to be closed, one can intervene into the simulation model, modify, apply this change, simulate and see the impact that the incident has and in the surrounding network. This simulation can also be used to generate response plans. This requires the simulation model to be very well calibrated to accurately present the prevailing traffic conditions.

Figure 17: Flowchart depicting Real-time traffic management framework

Focusing on the supply predictions, especially the ones using data driven algorithm, Ynte presented how artificial intelligence can help in predicting traffic supply. The traffic supply prediction range from speeds, counts, flows to occupancy. This data can be extracted from multiple sources such as Induction loops, Bluetooth sensors, GPS or a combination of multiple sources. In addition, the historical data of 1 year is usually required to capture all seasonal effects. On the other hand, minimum 2-3 months of data is required for developing the first predictive model.

Dataset speed Greater Manchester

Figure 18: Data set showing speed in 5-minute time stamp for Greater Manchester through loop detectors

An example was shared for Greater Manchester (see figure above), about dataset of speeds (corresponding to a historical dataset of 13 months with a 5 minute time stamp) on different locations with loop detectors. The interest was in predicting traffic speed for the next 5 minutes, 10 minutes or more (until 12 steps ahead i.e., 1 hour ahead in time). Later, the input for obtaining traffic supply output was shared. This includes historical and real-time data, external features (e.g., weather, road etc.), time series data and deep learning model (including temporal forecasting and spatial aggregation). Following this, Ynte shared the ability of the model to predict without incoming data by comparing predictions and ground truth observations. Data issues (e.g., data sets containing noise) relating to the task were also shared, such as fluctuations in travel time, which can be due to multiple reasons (e.g., Bluetooth sensors not detecting different modes which makes it harder to distinguish between speed of pedestrians' vs speed of vehicles).

Ynte shared how detection of anomalies is being done within the TANGENT project, which are defined as non-recurrent congestion (i.e., caused by accidents, roadworks). This relates to identification of location and impact analysis of identified events in a simulation environment. To determine anomalies, statistics for each sensor (for each location in the data set) is recorded such as 'expected mean error', 'expected median error', 'expected maximum error' and 'expected standard error'. This is followed by Anomaly Scores, which captures the deviation between the predictions and the observations. The machine learning algorithm is later used to define one score that in the end will notify if there's an anomaly detected. Following this, an example for the Athens Case Study was shared where the anomalies were mapped on location.

After the first presentation by Ynte (from IMEC) and Athina (from AIMSUN), questions were directed to the Advisory Board Members based on the topics covered via the Miro Board platform (see Figure below). The first question focused on the anomaly detection linked with the supply forecasting, where AB Members were asked the type of anomalies that are interesting to detect according to them. While the non-recurrent congestion conditions were mentioned earlier, recurrent congestion conditions were also open to be suggested if the AB Members found it to be interesting for the anomaly detection.

Prior to answering the questions, an AB member asked how the speakers interpreted the term 'anomaly', to have a common ground of understanding. Ynte responded that they interpret anomaly as a situation that causes a non-recurrent congestion. This does not include the normal rush hours causing congestion, but mainly events like accidents, other events in the city that disturb regular traffic patterns or more. Athina further added that anomalies are not restricted to car traffic but can also include the public transport services. Ynte supported the statement by sharing how they are incorporating forecasts for buses as well in relation to the general bus schedule.

An AB member suggested abnormal driving conditions, abnormal travel times, vehicles with abnormal behaviours, abnormal traffic volume as interesting anomalies to detect. Another AB member suggested vehicle breakdown in tunnels, heavy duty transport to building sites and bus/train delays to be detected. One member responded that, considering the shared road space between vehicles and public transport, detecting variation from planned time schedule should be an anomaly. Other responses from the AB members included events that may interrupt typical flow of traffic in the area and detecting propagation of anomaly in adjacent network areas.

Figure 19: Miro Board frame used for the first discussion session

Following the first question, Ynte also asked if there were any current challenges in the detection of the anomalies. Whether availability of no data is an issue, or other issues such as it being based on visuals etc. can be considered as well. To this an AB member suggested lack of access to floating vehicle data as one of the main challenges. Another member mentioned vehicles which are not connected and do not deliver data on the environment to be a challenge for the anomaly detection. Further, the member added the lack of data about the disruption event to be a challenge. Other challenges mentioned by the AB members included difficulty in determining the type of anomaly and its impact on the network, and high rates of false positives.

Considering the interpretation of the situation and mitigation actions, AB Members were asked for their priorities towards visualisation. To this, AB Members responded with visualisation on maps and crowd counts (if they were abnormal) as the ‘most important’ category followed by availability of alternative mobility services between ‘somewhat important’ and ‘least important’.

To generate response/mitigation plans, AB Members were asked about the main information/input they would use. One member responded with the ‘availability of alternatives (including other modes of transport)’ and ‘priorities of affected network users (if relevant)’, while another member noted ‘historical data on situations (i.e., how they were handled and its effects)’ and ‘information of the affected vehicles (types of operation, type of vehicle, etc.) to be able to prioritise, support etc.’ as the main input. In addition, connection with road planners, emergency services, PT control tower, radio information processing and social network processing were noted as the main information to be prioritised. Other information/input from the AB Members for the generation of response/mitigation plans included ‘detailed information of the conditions that led to the need for a response plan’ and ‘intended actions/resources, etc. of the different stakeholders responsible for the development of the plan’.

With focus on the real-time traffic monitoring, supply forecasting and anomaly detection, AB Members were asked what the main data-issues were according to them. Their response included data-

ownership, data quality and completeness, lack of standardised representation of data and standardised data quality, GDPR, unavailability of digitised information, uncertainties regarding liability in case of wrong data, inaccessibility of data sources (making it difficult to find and use them), and harmonisation of data as main challenges.

Towards the end, an AB member shared further ideas with the partners and other AB members. They expressed how in some control centres of public transport mixed with services; tasks were done without the digitization tools. While there is a lot of information which is incoming visually, the decision is made between different range of people and the communication is done through radio. This results in a lot of data not being digitised. An example was shared, where a jam on a traffic line is followed by the control centre notifying the patrol police to act. The information on notification is usually not available digitally. Hence, when the traffic follows a normal flow, the reason behind the solution is usually unknown (i.e., whether it was solved due to natural management of the situation or due to human intervention). This behaviour is not captured unless one has the information. It is therefore important to know if there has been a human intervention in certain situations, and that should be included in the prediction model. The integration of social media platforms in the control centre was also mentioned, where a dedicated screen is used to track real-time information via the social media posts (e.g., twitter posts sharing a metro line being stuck). They also shared how the planning of the trash trucks is dynamically changing, which is also important to detect the reason behind jams. From a simulation perspective, Athina conveyed the importance of anomaly to be confirmed first. And with the example of trash trucks being a recurring event, it is important to consider during data mining to analyse historical data. To counter this, one AB member objected that the allocation of trash truck services is usually randomly planned and hence it is difficult to make it a recurrent event. As a solution, a partnership with the responsible company doing the planning and utilising the plan was proposed.

3.3.6 AB Session 5: Initial results obtained testing individual components + Modelling of Stakeholder opinions and the formation of consensus

Antonio David Masegosa from DEUSTO and Marios Giouroukelis from NTUA gave the presentation for the session. Antonio introduced the preliminary results for the Transport Network Optimization System in this presentation by focusing on TANGENT Service and Functionalities. With higher complexity of multimodal transport network management, new tools were required to support decision makers. This included generation of transport policy and response plans using Computer Optimised Design (COD). This would be based on artificial intelligence along with transport modelling consensus reaching mechanisms. 4 different use cases related to the response plans were presented which include integration of DRT and Transit modes, synchronisation of Public Transport (PT) and Traffic Control, Signal vehicle coupled control with CAVs, and Dynamic Congestion pricing.

The flowchart of the tool focusing on COD and consensus reaching mechanisms was shared (see Figure below). The simulations lead to the generation to certain KPIs, which can relate to average delay in the network, emissions, congestion in specific areas, energy consumption of vehicles and more. This is followed by 'weighted sum' which also receives input from consensus reaching mechanism, which provides a weight towards the opinion of different stakeholders in the management of an event. This assists to provide a level of relevance to each of the KPIs that must be considered. This process is followed by a termination criterion, which results in a near optimal solution.

Based on the use-cases, an overview of integration of DRT and transit modes was shared, where the first/last-mile problems can affect the use of PT in areas where the service is less frequent. The TANGENT approach was to apply COD to determine optimal or near optimal DRT fleet and operational routes to serve the first/last mile of an area. The performance indicators include percentage of demand served, total emissions produced by the DRT fleet, operational costs of the DRT service, and average travel time for passengers (first mile + PT trip + last mile). This use case was tested in the Athens case study, considering the connection between Thrakomakedones region and the First District of Athens. 200 trip requests were generated (100 in each sense) randomly within specified areas, with departure

time windows in the interval 08:00-14:00. Preliminary test results were shared for the performance indicators, including average passengers' travel time for PT and combination of PT and DRT.

The tools: Computer Optimized Design & Consensus Reaching Mechanisms

Figure 20: Flowchart of tools including COD and consensus reaching mechanisms

Considering the second use case of synchronisation of PT and Traffic Control, other problems of PT were focused upon such as lack of flexibility to react to sudden changes in demand and supply. The TANGENT approach was readjusting the frequency and/or capacity of some surface PT lines and traffic control plan simultaneously upon planned or unplanned events (e.g., failure of a metro line). The performance indicators considered included user costs of the affected PT lines, operational costs of PT fleet, congestion in some predefined areas, and reduction of the system wide emissions. The preliminary test in Greater Manchester was presented showing the AIMSUN model with 10 PT bus lines and 24 signalised nodes.

The third use case of signal vehicle coupled control with CAVs was presented, where the focus and assumptions were mentioned prior to TANGENT approach and performance indicators. The TANGENT approach included applying COD to optimise the path assignment for the complete CAV fleet and the traffic control plan on specific arterials of the considered network. The performance indicators included system-wide emissions, congestion in selected areas, travel time difference between CAVs and conventional vehicles, and total energy consumption of CAVs. The preliminary test in Greater Manchester was presented showing the identified indicators with reduction in emissions and congestion but increase in travel time difference between CAVs and conventional vehicles, and total energy consumption of CAVs.

Following this, Marios presented the topic of consensus mechanism development. With difficulty in reaching consensus-based decisions, a solution is provided with needs of different stakeholders addressed. The TANGENT consensus mechanism objectives were presented which included creating a decision-support tool to facilitate decision making with state-of-the-art data-driven models trained on stakeholder preferences and more. Data collection through cooperation specifications and opinions (including paired preferences) were shared. Regarding actual treatment of opinions, different steps were presented which included a fuzzy c-means clustering approach (to identify most prominent opinions, clustering it to majority and minority clusters), using a Bayesian network (to create stakeholder graph identifying probability to communicate with other stakeholders), using opinion dynamic (to

investigate opinion exchange), using consensus reach process (CRP) framework (to modify opinion through arbitration), and finally to derive the weights of the objectives from the opinion matrix of each problem.

After the presentation by Antonio (from DEUSTO) and Marios (from NTUA), questions were directed to the Advisory Board Members based on the topics covered via the Miro Board platform. The first question focused on the testing of the individual components, where the AB Members were asked their opinion towards the results shown in each use case presented. The three use cases (excluding the Dynamic congestion pricing) included 'Integration of Demand Responsive Transport and Transit Modes', 'Synchronization of Public Transport and Traffic Control', and 'Signal vehicle coupled control with CAVs'. There were 5 response categories for the AB Members namely 'Outstanding', 'Promising', 'Nice', 'Poor' and 'Unrealistic'. Antonio stressed that these are preliminary results, and in TANGENT the idea was to later test on a larger scale.

In 'Integration of Demand Responsive Transport and Transit Modes', all Advisory Board Members responded with the result to be 'promising'. Similar response was recorded for the second use-case i.e., 'Synchronization of Public Transport and Traffic Control', where the results were categorised as 'promising'. Considering the third use-case, i.e., 'Signal vehicle coupled control with CAVs', two members categorised the result as 'nice' while two other members categorised the result as 'promising'. Antonio supported the response as they acknowledged the 45% share of CAVs in comparison to 65% for conventional vehicles within the proof-of-testing framework.

Following this, an AB member mentioned that considering the prospect of collecting the information with the connected and automated vehicles, we are still distant from that situation. Realistically, it is nice but if everything is well controlled it has the potential to be promising or even outstanding. Antonio agreed with the statement, and recollected how an AB member in the previous AB Meeting had mentioned the framework with CAVs connected to the traffic management can be challenging, in terms of missing information that needs to be exchanged.

Considering the follow-up question on suggestions to improve the use-cases, an AB member mentioned in relation to the third use-case, that it could also be relevant if the vehicles are connected but not automated. Athina added that considering connected and automated vehicles, it doesn't necessarily mean that they had modelled the behaviour of the vehicles to act as autonomous for this experiment. They had assumed that the vehicles are connected in terms of receiving information influencing the decision.

The third question by NTUA focused on the consensus mechanism where the Advisory Board members were asked if the developed system accurately reflected the real decision-making process followed by stakeholders, in situations like choosing the best traffic light signalling for a major road. One AB member agreed with the developed system reflecting the process, while others mentioned it reflected the process partially. They added it would be nice to see the operational experience about the developed system. Corresponding to the third question, an Advisory Board member suggested an evaluation stage following deployment of a response action could help to enhance the authenticity of the simulated decision-making process.

3.3.7 AB Session 6: Update on Case Studies and current situation + current technical challenges in implementation + first preliminary results

Lucie Tristant from ID4MOBILITY led the presentation in the Advisory Board Meeting. A case study overview of the four cities i.e., Lisbon, Greater Manchester, Rennes, and Athens was presented. The environment of testing was defined in each case study, which included different scenarios where the TANGENT services are going to be used, planned and unplanned events, along with the baseline scenario. For all the case studies, the baseline scenario was the 'daily commuting on a typical working day during morning and afternoon peak hours'. The planned events varied for different case studies.

For instance, in Lisbon the music festival was included in planned events while unplanned roadworks, accidents and PT strikes were considered under unplanned events. While, in Greater Manchester the planned events included football matches and concerts, followed by traffic collisions and incidents causing lane closure as one of the unplanned events. The Athens case study is a virtual case study which leads to differences in the functionalities as compared to the other case studies.

Following the overview of the case studies, Lucie presented the challenges in the implementation of the case studies. Each service functionality requires components to be developed, tested by the case studies, and be implemented in the overall platform: Dashboard, Data or TANGENT API, Anomalous Event detection, Supply Forecasting. For each component and scenario, identification of the type of data is to be provided by the case studies for its development by the technical partners.

In addition, Lucie shared the present status of the overall platform. The project was towards the end of the testing of the subsystems (in this period of time), which resulted in the overall platform to be tested in 2024. The timeline for subsystems testing in different Work Packages were shared for the months of October, November, and December 2023. To proceed with the testing and to obtain good feedback, certain parameters were utilised to test the subsystems. These included the foreseen testing dates, the stakeholders involved in the testing, testing typology (remotely), communication with the stakeholders (synchronous / asynchronous), requirements and a testing methodology. The objective was to have these tests done by the end of 2023 and have feedback from technical partners.

In the end examples of methodologies were shared from the technical partners, who proposed methodologies adapted to their components and case study examples. The first example included synchronisation of public transport and traffic control (provided by DEUSTO). The methodology included preparation phase, followed by scenario simulation and result analysis, and feedback from case study leaders. The second example included travel behaviour module testing (provided by NTUA). The methodology included a travel behaviour survey with 10 people per use case, following guidelines to have varying profiles. The next steps included testing of the platform, which workshops in the process, to see that the platform had functionalities expected by the case studies (including the elements on the Dashboard for the potential end users). This was carried out after the testing of the subsystems.

For the discussion session, after the presentation by Lucie (from ID4CAR), questions were directed to the Advisory Board Members based on the topics covered via the Miro Board platform. Considering the case study cities in the project, AB members were asked if they had any questions about the case study environments such as scenarios, data sharing, etc.

In relation to the Athens case study, one member asked if the interface between TMC and CAV is directly or via CAV FMS. To this, Charis Chalkiadakis (from NTUA) responded that Athens is a virtual case study where everything is executed in a simulated environment that they are using. It was not something that they could respond to based on the framework of the project action in Athens. In regard to exchanging information between a traffic management centre and a fleet of vehicles that move in an urban transportation network, all the exchange of information needs to be done by making use of all the necessary protocols in terms of exchanging infrastructure to vehicle messages. For a real-life pilot it would be done by all necessary RSU equipment.

Focusing on the Rennes case study, one member asked if there was any information exchange with the fleet operators managing the freight transport. To this, Lucie responded that they didn't have sensors that could detect specifically vehicles for freight. It is difficult to identify and measure how many vehicles are dedicated to the freight transport in the flows. It was not considered within the scope of the TANGENT case study, but there are chances for it to be covered in the next steps. To this, Leire added that none of the case studies had specific functionalities for freight transport.

Following this, the final question of the session for the AB members was in relation to ways to address the integration challenges of multimodal transportation systems, considering different technologies and

infrastructures involved. The responses included many suggestions regarding standards such as having a body to verify data quality and to verify the compliance with standards, standardised interfaces, and investigation into the possibility of using existing standards. Other suggestions included common understanding and definition of the expected data, along with the proposal of a decentralised architecture that may allow a continuous improvement of the solution.

4 Policy Recommendation Workshop

4.1 Introduction

The policy recommendation workshop was part of the activities planned within Task 1.3 Stakeholder Engagement and Consultation, which aimed to bring forward a platform to discuss policy implications and derive key recommendations and lessons learned from TANGENT's results and outputs. This will also provide a key input to D8.5 in WP8.

4.2 Agenda and approach

The on-site workshop was set up in a World Café format, focusing on three key aspects. The guiding questions for the three aspects are listed below:

1. Exploitation of MTM solutions / TANGENT Tools

Guiding questions:

- Drivers and barriers to MTM implementation: Which benefits were perceived by the CS? Which were evidenced in the test results? Which key challenges needed to be overcome and could hinder upscaling?
- Business models for the exploitation of TANGENT Tools: Which are viable use cases for the commercialisation of the TANGENT exploitable results? What are the prerequisites for any city interested in implementing TANGENT's MTM solutions? (consider, data availability, digital infrastructure, transport models, governance structure and stakeholder engagement, strategic background, etc.)

2. Policies and regulations: Gaps and recommendations

Guiding questions:

- How could new policies and regulations support MTM solutions? (e.g., establish data sharing standards and requirements for public service operators, determine data governance and management parameters, encourage a culture of co-operation rather than competition among involved actors).
- How can we ensure that the proposed MTM solutions and the resulting management measures effectively address real user needs and local policy goals?
- How could we encourage the use of such digital tools for transport planning. not just management? How could MTM and SUMP processes relate and support each other?

3. Further research needs and open questions

Guiding questions:

- What are the next steps for TANGENT's MTM solutions? Are there any additional scenarios or functionalities relevant to better address the needs of cities and regions?
- Do you think municipalities are equipped to manage these systems?
- What support/capacities are required from cities and regions to deploy TANGENT's MTM solutions?
- MTM Roadmap: TANGENT contribution and next steps? Traffic management in the light of connectivity (CCAM)

4.3 Insights from the workshop

4.3.1 Exploitation of MTM solutions / TANGENT Tools

The workshop was structured around three core questions, focusing on drivers and barriers towards MTM implementation looking on the benefits (with evidence in the test results) and key challenges hindering the upscaling of the solutions developed; and business models for the exploitation of TANGENT tools focusing on viable use cases for commercialization and prerequisites for solution implementation.

4.3.1.1 Drivers and barriers to MTM implementation

One of the primary benefits identified is the collaborative potential that MTM offers for local stakeholders, especially in terms of shared Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as CO₂ emissions reduction. These KPIs facilitate informed decision-making among stakeholders, allowing them to forecast and adapt public transport routes in real-time. The TANGENT data catalogue is instrumental in achieving this, offering several advantages:

- Use case partners can clearly articulate and structure the data they manage.
- The specific metadata profile (TANGENT metadata) assists in identifying data gaps and format compatibility issues, prompting improvements in data availability and harmonisation.
- The framework facilitates the inclusion of external data, enabling a comprehensive, accurate representation of datasets.

Moreover, MTM provides enhanced integration of various data channels, contributing to a standardised and improved data catalogue. This integration addresses new functionalities not previously available in Network Traffic Management (NTM), shifting the focus from isolated results to a process-driven approach that fosters better communication among stakeholders. This cooperative environment, which was less common before, supports a consolidated operational view where KPIs and indicators are universally visible and accessible across the system. By enabling predictive scenarios for various transport modes through a multimodal approach, MTM enhances decision-making capabilities for multiple stakeholders.

Additionally, the visualisation aspects of MTM play a critical role in situational awareness, where real-time data integration enables a platform for continuous monitoring and adaptability. As more data sources are added, the system's usability expands, allowing for scalable solutions through the integration of multimodal transport data and intuitive user interface options. The user-friendly nature and customisable functionalities ensure that users can tailor the tool to meet specific requirements, promoting efficient interaction with the system.

Key Barriers to MTM Implementation

Despite these benefits, significant barriers remain in implementing MTM. One major obstacle is the shortage of manpower and technical capacity within use cases, particularly for testing, maintaining, and validating data. Furthermore, the absence of robust multimodal datasets, including a lack of historical data for more informed decision-making, hampers accurate analysis. Operational challenges such as extended simulation times, time constraints in result exchange, and incompatibility with existing tools used by stakeholders for public transport and traffic management were also highlighted.

Transport modelling was another key challenge. In some cases, the availability and quality of transport models were limited. For example, Rennes faced difficulties in adapting existing models, and there was a general lack of transport modelling skills across stakeholders. Key barriers to scaling MTM solutions include ensuring data availability and quality, maintaining consistent support from stakeholders and data owners, and addressing potential deprecation of functionalities. This latter issue demands periodic recalibration and validation of core models to keep functionalities relevant. Financing for ongoing research, data access and integration, political risks tied to governance and funding, and willingness to

support MTM approaches beyond project timelines are also critical challenges to the widespread adoption of MTM solutions. Upscaling MTM requires careful consideration of these complexities to ensure that tools meet city-specific needs and can be sustained in the long term.

4.3.1.2 *Business models for the exploitation of TANGENT Tools*

Commercialisation Use Cases and Exploitable Results

The TANGENT tools, particularly the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) on data harmonisation and fusion, offer extensive commercialisation potential across different sectors, including logistics and transport. These tools can be configured for various mobility sectors, providing solutions that enable efficient sharing and utilisation of heterogeneous data sources. For instance, a significant commercialisation use case includes integrating the tool with digital twin environments. This approach enhances configurability, allowing for customisable scenarios and incident planning tools tailored to specific city needs. By establishing a toolkit of scenario-based solutions, TANGENT tools could be replicated in similar urban areas, enabling easier deployment across various cities.

Further, historical data visualisation capabilities within TANGENT present an attractive use case. By enabling stakeholders to review and analyse past events (e.g., incidents from days or weeks prior), the tool offers valuable insights for urban planning and operational adjustments. For cities with established collaboration practices and KPI tracking mechanisms, TANGENT tools provide additional utility by facilitating optimisation modules that supplement existing simulation tools with ad-hoc functionalities.

In situations where cities may not wish to overhaul their current systems, TANGENT's engagement with key project partners, such as A-to-Be and AIMSUN, allows for incremental integration. These companies can potentially embed TANGENT's core functionalities into their respective tools, offering cities an opportunity to adopt MTM capabilities without significant system restructuring.

Exploitation Drivers and Prerequisites for MTM Implementation

Stakeholder engagement remains a central driver of TANGENT tool exploitation. However, a lack of stakeholder involvement can also become a barrier. Maintaining active engagement with local and regional stakeholders is essential for the success and continuity of MTM solutions.

For cities looking to implement TANGENT's MTM solutions, several prerequisites are critical. Firstly, a well-defined strategic vision of the city's goals, potential conflicts, and operational needs is essential. Data catalogues that offer structured data and updated transport models must be available to support MTM operations. Additionally, cities must consider socio-economic factors, which may influence the extent to which MTM solutions can be customised to local contexts. Digital infrastructure, such as robust data-sharing platforms and transport modelling tools, is also crucial for the successful implementation of TANGENT solutions. The governance structure within the city, along with stakeholder involvement, serves as another fundamental prerequisite. Effective governance models can help navigate political challenges and secure the necessary funding to support MTM operations beyond the initial deployment phase. Continuous collaboration with stakeholders ensures that the MTM solutions align with city priorities and can be scaled over time.

4.3.2 **Policies and regulations: Gaps and recommendations**

The workshop session was structured around three core questions, focusing on the role of new policies in enabling MTM solutions, ensuring that these solutions address real user needs and local goals, and promoting the integration of MTM tools with Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning (SUMP) processes. The following sections provide an in-depth analysis based on the discussions.

4.3.2.1 *Gaps in existing policies and regulations*

Data Sharing Standards and Accessibility

The workshop highlighted a significant gap in established standards for data sharing, which affects cooperation between public and private actors:

- **Inconsistent Standards Across Operators:** Public transport and city planners often lack well-recognized data standards. Variability in standards complicates procurement processes, with operators facing challenges integrating systems across multiple vendors.
- **Lack of mature National Access Points (NAPs):** In many European cities, National Access Points (NAPs) for data sharing are underdeveloped. A mature NAP is essential for seamless data sharing across cities and between stakeholders, yet funding and operational models remain inconsistent.
- **Barriers for Private Operators in Data Sharing:** Private entities, especially in logistics and micro-mobility, are often hesitant to share data due to concerns about business confidentiality and the lack of incentives. Current regulations do not adequately address how these entities can safely share data without risking competitive advantage.

Governance and Role Allocation

Clear role definition in data governance is lacking, which creates challenges in data management:

- **Unclear Roles in Data Ownership and Management:** There is insufficient guidance on who should manage, store, and control access to data in MTM systems. This creates barriers in determining accountability for data accuracy, security, and compliance with regulations like GDPR.
- **Need for a Central Coordinating Entity:** Suggestions on cities benefitting from a central authority responsible for managing MTM data governance, ensuring that data collection, storage, and sharing protocols are standardized. An example is the Netherlands' [National Data Warehouse](#) where Dutch authorities collaborate on the collection, integration, storage, and distribution of mobility data. The data from and about road traffic is collected monitoring its quality, it is enriched, stored, and made available. This was a top-down approach, allowing many stakeholders and bodies to join the platform.

Security and Privacy Concerns

Data security emerged as a top concern, especially for private stakeholders:

- **Insufficient Cybersecurity Measures:** While data privacy (e.g., GDPR compliance) is prioritized, there is often less focus on robust cybersecurity for shared data platforms, which poses risks in MTM implementations.
- **Need for Privacy Standards for Sensitive Data:** Data governance policies must address the handling of sensitive data, particularly business-sensitive data, to foster trust and ensure privacy without inhibiting data sharing.

4.3.2.2 Recommendations to Address Identified Gaps

Establishing Comprehensive Data Standards

- **Unified Data Standards for Public Procurement:** Policymakers should work to establish unified data standards across the EU that align with ITS directives, specifically for MTM. This would streamline procurement and support interoperability across multiple vendors and operators.
- **Developing and Strengthening NAPs:** Investment in developing mature, functional NAPs across all EU member states is essential. These should support real-time data sharing and facilitate interoperability between national and regional data sources.
- **Incentives for Data Sharing from Private Operators:** To encourage private actors to share data, incentives such as subsidies, tax benefits, or simplified data-sharing agreements could be implemented. Additionally, defining clear data-sharing protocols can minimize competitive risks for private operators.

Improving Governance Models for Data Management

- **Creating a Central Coordinating Body for MTM Data:** A central governance entity within cities or regions could manage data sharing, resolve disputes, and enforce standards. This body would facilitate cooperation among stakeholders by defining and overseeing responsibilities.
- **Defining Clear Access Levels and Permissions:** Data governance frameworks should establish access hierarchies, ensuring that only authorized personnel have access to certain types of data. This approach would help balance privacy concerns and data accessibility.

Enhancing Security and Privacy in Data Governance

- **Incorporating Cybersecurity Protocols in MTM Systems:** A data governance policy for MTM must include mandatory cybersecurity measures to protect data from breaches. This would involve regular audits, encryption, and real-time monitoring of data access.
- **Regulations for Sensitive Data Handling:** To secure sensitive business data, specific privacy standards should be introduced that define how such data can be shared, stored, and managed, with attention to GDPR compliance.

4.3.2.3 Integrating MTM with Local Policy Goals and User Needs

Configurable MTM Solutions

The workshop emphasized the need for MTM solutions that can adapt to changing user needs and local policy updates:

- **Customization and Flexibility:** Configurable MTM tools should be designed to allow easy modifications based on local policy changes, user needs, and evolving transportation goals. This flexibility would help MTM solutions remain relevant despite dynamic urban environments and also allow possibilities for it to be transferred to a different city.
- **User-Centric Data Indicators:** Incorporating user-focused indicators, such as liveability or accessibility indexes, would help align MTM solutions with real community needs and sustainability goals.

Regular Engagement with Stakeholders

- **Continuous Feedback Mechanisms:** Establishing regular channels for feedback from end users, city planners, and private operators is essential for aligning MTM solutions with user requirements. A collaborative feedback loop would facilitate the early identification of gaps or evolving needs in traffic management.
- **On-Site Testing and Local Adaptation:** Engaging with local transport authorities to test MTM tools on-site before full implementation allows solutions to be tailored to local conditions. This hands-on approach would improve the tool's efficacy and ensure it meets local expectations.

4.3.2.4 Encouraging the Use of MTM for Transport Planning

Integration of MTM and SUMP Processes

- **Coordinated Planning and Operations:** SUMP processes, which emphasize long-term sustainable urban mobility planning, should integrate MTM data and tools to support transport planning as well as real-time management. The data collected through MTM can provide valuable insights into modal shifts, congestion patterns, and user preferences, guiding SUMP initiatives.
- **Scenario-Based Planning Tools:** MTM solutions should incorporate scenario libraries and simulation tools for transport planning, enabling cities to anticipate the impact of infrastructure developments or policy changes on real-time mobility.

Developing Impact Assessment Frameworks

- Performance Indicators for Policy Alignment: MTM tools should be designed to measure and report on specific KPIs that align with local policy objectives, such as reduced emissions, improved public transport usage, or decreased travel times.
- Cost-Benefit and Sustainability Analysis: Integrating a cost-benefit analysis within MTM tools can help quantify the benefits of MTM in transport planning, ensuring that investments support long-term sustainability.

4.3.3 Further research needs and open questions

New data sources and their challenges

- Integration of new sources, such as Floating Car Data (FCD)
- Development of new models to facilitate data harmonisation and overcome integration and interoperability issues
- Suitable methodologies and functionalities for the processing of larger volumes of data and its technical/operational requirements
- Further research and methodologies to evaluate the consistency and accuracy of data sets
- Scale-up of the multimodality character of the solution, by including further modes (e.g., active modes – pedestrians and bicycle)
- Model training for network-wide predictions based on newly integrated data sources

Further testing and enhancement of MTM solutions

- Reduction of processing times for optimisation modules to enable faster and more flexible assessment of solutions
- Evaluation of new scenarios and use cases for cooperative traffic management, enabling the validation and optimisation of MTM response plans on local level
- Large-scale pilots/demonstrations
- Knowledge exchange and possible integration with freight and logistics solutions
- Expansion of MTM, Digital Infrastructure and Digital Twin solutions: through the project's experience, participants have seen the potential for upscaling and further pursuing MTM solutions, e.g., through Digital Twins, to integrating real-time traffic data to optimize city planning and traffic flow.

MTM solutions as enabler of new mobility planning practices

- Regularity of data collection and monitoring to steer collaborative mobility planning between public and private stakeholders, establishing cooperation structures that enable strategic alignment and preparation of MTM response plans and operational coordination.
- Strengthen SUMP implementation and monitoring phases, steering stakeholder engagement and cooperation through the implementation phase, based on continuous data collection and traffic management efforts.
- Establish clearer governance frameworks that define roles and responsibilities among stakeholders, particularly during incidents, based on the roles and tasks considered for TANGENT's case studies. This could involve developing policies that ensure all operators respond consistently and effectively to disruptions.

Capacity building and support for broad uptake of MTM solutions

- Provide training for transport operators and city authorities on the use of new tools and data systems to ensure smooth adoption and maximize the benefits of traffic management innovations, understanding the challenges of a transition towards new working practices and technological environments.

5 TANGENT Forum activities on Mobility Academy

5.1 Introduction to the Mobility Academy

The TANGENT Forum is a space on Mobility Academy for members to access further information about the project and share knowledge and expertise to the project partners and other members of the Forum. It establishes a structured cooperation strategy involving various organisations, researchers, authorities across Europe to engage in consultation for mutual benefit.

Aiming to maximise outreach, TANGENT follows a primarily virtual approach for its stakeholder engagement activities (involving Webinars, forum engagement, project updates, participation and discussion platform, offers more opportunities for knowledge exchange). The user forum engagement is hosted in the Rupprecht's [Mobility-Academy platform](https://mobility-academy.eu) (mobility-academy.eu) which has been successfully utilised in several EC projects (e.g., SUMP-UP). The platform provides opportunity for the forum participants to:

- have an overview on the engagement activities ongoing, especially related to Webinars, where the information is archived, and key insights are shared via **News and Announcements**
- follow-up and provide feedback through **Discussion Forums** for further knowledge exchange.
- have early access to registration for events like **Webinars**
- have a closed circle of feedback and exchanges, especially related to AB sessions (this section was reserved for Advisory Board members exclusively)

5.1.1 Invitations and interface

Prior to the kickstart of the Webinar series, the Advisory Board members were invited to join the TANGENT Forum for the AB session activities, where the minutes and other details of the sessions were shared with all members; and later they had access to the TANGENT Forum activities.

Following the initiation of the discussion forums and Webinar series, the interested participants from the Webinars were later invited to the TANGENT Forum, excluding their access to the information and documents contained in the Advisory Board section. The Tangent Forum includes 5 major sections on the Mobility Academy (as seen in the figure below).

The TANGENT Forum sections are as follows:

4. **TANGENT Forum** (showing the overall homepage including discussion forum, news, and announcement as sub-sections),
5. **Advisory Board** (restricted to Advisory Board members having access to AB session minutes and exchanges),
6. **Webinars** (providing access to information on Webinars, recordings and minutes),
7. **TANGENT Results** (providing access to public deliverables and progress), and
8. **Case Studies** (providing information on four TANGENT case studies).

TANGENT Forum

The **TANGENT Forum** is the platform as a part of the Horizon, 2020 TANGENT Project that establishes a structured cooperation strategy involving various organisations, researchers, authorities across Europe to engage in consultation for mutually benefit.

The TANGENT project aims to develop new complementary tools for **optimising traffic operations** in a coordinated and dynamic way from a **multimodal perspective** and considering **automated/non-automated vehicles, passengers and freight transport**. TANGENT will research on advanced techniques on modelling and simulation, such as prediction and simulation models for future demand & supply of transport; optimisation techniques for balancing the demand flows between the means of transport; and users travel behaviour modelling.

This Forum is a space for members to **access further information** about the project and **share knowledge and expertise** to the project partners and other members of the Forum.

At the moment, participation in this space is **by invitation only**.

Course Settings Participants Grades Reports More

Advisory Board TANGENT Results

Webinars

A series of webinars will be held, presenting key project results and the tools developed, and collecting feedback from key stakeholders.

PAGE
Webinar 1: Navigating through Network and Traffic Management: An Urban Phenomenon (November 2023)

Figure 21: TANGENT Forum Sections on Mobility Academy

5.1.2 Knowledge exchange opportunities

Kickstarting the Tangent Forum activities, an article was published on the discussion forum sharing the progress on Smart Infrastructure Classification Index. The participants were given access to the information on SICI and given a platform to discuss further on the topic with the authors. Following this, through a series of Webinars, the discussion forum on follow-up, summary and information on Webinars was created and shared, where participants were given the opportunity to ask any further questions which they might've missed during the live Webinar event.

For the Webinars, the information was updated on a timely basis post live-Webinar events for the section and sub-sections, which included the description, speaker information, webinar recording, and proceedings including the minutes from the event. After every Webinar, participants were encouraged to register for the TANGENT Forum, where access to presentation minutes, recordings, and information was made available.

The Webinar recordings were also made available on TANGENT project's YouTube page as follows (link provided in the title):

- [Webinar 1](#): Navigating through Network and Traffic Management: An Urban Phenomenon,
- [Webinar 2](#): Real-Time Traffic Modelling and Forecasting Tools,
- [Webinar 3](#): Transport Network Optimisation and Arbitration Models, and

- Webinar 4: Integrated Tool for Cooperative Traffic Management and Results of Case Study Implementation.

Figure 22: Discussion Forum on Smart Infrastructure Classification Index

Snapshots from project deliverables were provided in the TANGENT Results section contributing towards the project objectives. Examples from the deliverable snapshots can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 23: Snapshots from project deliverables as provided by POLIS

6 Conclusions

The TANGENT project has laid the groundwork for multi-actor cooperation models in network traffic management (NTM). Through webinars, case studies, and expert advisory board meetings, the project has facilitated knowledge exchange and explored challenges faced by cities in implementing multi-modal traffic solutions. The various sessions emphasised the need for data sharing, collaboration between public and private sectors, and creating standardised frameworks to ensure interoperability in transport systems.

The advisory board sessions revealed gaps in data governance, quality, and the necessity for integrating real-time data with existing infrastructure, particularly in urban contexts. The discussions during webinars and workshops helped identify opportunities for optimization in traffic flow, and use of advanced simulation and machine learning tools for forecasting and decision-making. The sessions also explored potential barriers to adopting TANGENT's solutions and provided recommendations to address these.

The co-creation efforts demonstrated through the workshops, including in-depth case studies in cities like Greater Manchester, Lisbon, and Rennes, highlighted how tailored strategies can be developed for cities with different challenges, but with a shared goal of sustainable and efficient traffic management. The project has paved the way for future research by identifying open questions and laying out recommendations for policy and regulations.

Moving forward, the lessons learned through TANGENT emphasise the importance of continued cooperation among stakeholders and leveraging technology-driven solutions to create more efficient, sustainable urban transport systems.

7 References

Mobility Academy at <https://www.mobility-academy.eu/>

Rupprecht Consult (2019), Guidelines for Developing and Implementing a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan, Second Edition, Retrieved from:
https://www.eltis.org/sites/default/files/sump_guidelines_2019_interactive_document_1.pdf